

Does the Decline of the Canadian Manufacturing Sector Matter?

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Abstract

In this paper, we first analyze the historical data for the Canadian manufacturing sector, in terms of output and employment. We can clearly see this sector is declining, especially after the early 2000s. We then explore the causes for the decline and find that import competition and offshoring explain a large proportion of the decline, especially after China joined WTO in 2001. Whether or not this decline matters, our evidence shows manufacturing has unrivaled importance for the health of the economy, the labour market, international trade, global competitiveness, social and political impacts, as well as supply chain security and national security. We conclude that not only does the manufacturing decline and low level of output matter, but it is urgent for the government to come up with a multi-faceted strategy to reverse the trend and revitalize the sector. As the world is entering a fourth industrial revolution, it is vital to have a healthy and growing manufacturing sector. Based on our findings, we propose a ten-year vision for the Canadian manufacturing sector, and provide a set of realistic policy suggestions for the government to consider.

1. Introduction

From the 1960s to the late 1990s, both the nominal and real output of the manufacturing sector in Canada showed firm growth, although the growth fell short of overall GDP such that manufacturing output as a share of GDP declined on a trend basis in both nominal and real terms. The real output kept pace with the business sector during those four decades. However, after the early 2000s, both real and nominal output of the manufacturing sector (which had been moving upward for decades) stagnated suddenly. It declined further during the 2008 financial crisis and the ensuing recession. And until recently, the nominal output barely reached the levels of 20 years ago. As of 2018, the real output was still about 10% below the previous peak.

Regarding the share of total GDP, the nominal and real manufacturing output have moved along the downward trend. From the highest levels during the 1960s, the nominal and real shares of GDP dropped to

the historical lows in 2018 by around 12 and 16 percentage points respectively from the above 20% level. The manufacturing employment share in national total employment lost around 10 percentage points to 9%, which is also unprecedentedly low. Of note, the downtrend of both output share and employment accelerated since the early 2000s. These trends after the 2009 recession, though slightly better, saw little sign of reversal from those low levels.

One may wonder what caused the decline and whether it matters, considering that Canada is one of the major industrialized countries (for example, the G7). Some may question contemporary implications of the decline. For example, what does the decline of the manufacturing sector mean to the macroeconomy? Is the decline of the manufacturing sector slowing the overall economic growth in Canada, depressing productivity and worsening the standard of living of Canadians? What does the decline mean to the labour market and income inequality? Could the decline in manufacturing explain the concomitant trade deficit and in turn, does the trade deficit matter? If these developments matter, how can and should the trend decline in manufacturing be reversed? Through the exploration of historical data, our research will investigate the causes and impacts, as well as possible policy suggestions.

The structure of this paper is as follows - Section 2 describes relevant historical data including manufacturing output, output share and employment, productivity, within the sector changes, and cross-country comparison. Section 3 investigates the causes of the decline. Section 4 analyzes the impacts of the decline, mainly on health of the economy, labour markets, international trade, global competitiveness and social issues. Lastly, Section 5 investigates the policy options.

2. Observations/Historical Data

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impacts of the decline of the manufacturing sector in Canada. This section will look at the data evidence to determine whether the manufacturing sector in Canada is or has been in decline over the past decades.

2.1 Measures of the decline of the manufacturing sector

Four measurements are used to examine the decline of the manufacturing sector: the output level in both real and nominal numbers, the output as a share of the total output in both real and nominal, the employment as an absolute number, and the employment as a share of the total employment in Canada. Of note, manufacturing output or employment in economic statistics are measured based on manufacturing

establishments (plants), not the entire company. It does not include a company’s R&D, management or sales departments. No backward or forward linkages of sectors are counted (Houseman 2018).

- Manufacturing output (in real or nominal numbers)

Figure 1. Nominal GDP, manufacturing, Canada, 1961-2015

Figure 2. Real GDP, manufacturing and business sector, Canada, 1961-2017

In Canada, the nominal manufacturing output was growing firmly from \$8.7 billion in 1961 to \$192.3 billion in 2000. Prior to 2000, the real manufacturing output was growing at a similar pace as the business sector (all private industries*). However, both nominal and real output growth stagnated from 2000 to 2004 and plummeted after 2004. From the time-series data of both figures, recessions caused by the 2008 global financial crisis seem to have further hit the manufacturing output and after the crisis, both nominal and real outputs showed recovery. In 2014, the nominal output nearly caught up with the level in 2000, whereas the real output never fully recovered to the 2000-year level. In this sense, the manufacturing sector in Canada during this period compared with the business sector can be called “the lost two decades” which means there has been barely growth in comparison to the 2000’s level. Note that from 1992 to 2000, the rapid growth of both outputs was much related to the Canadian dollar depreciation to the US dollar during the same period that reduced competitive pressures on Canadian manufacturers (Statistics Canada 2009, also see the analysis in Section 3.2 - Exchange Rate).

*The Canadian business sector is based on the Input-Output industry codes and includes BS11A0 to BS810 (http://www23.statcan.gc.ca/imdb-bmdi/document/1301_D2_T9_V1-eng.htm).

- Manufacturing output as a share of GDP (in real or nominal numbers)

Figure 3. Manufacturing's share of nominal GDP, 1961-2015

Figure 4. Manufacturing's share of the business sector GDP, 1961-2015

The manufacturing's share of the nominal total GDP in Canada followed a downward trend from around 21% in 1961 to 15% in 1992, which was mostly because of the price decrease of manufactured goods (Statistics Canada 2009). From the 1970s to 1990s, the share fluctuated in a relatively stable 14-18% range, in which from 1992 to 2000 the share rose from 14% to nearly 18% mostly due to exchange rate-induced price changes (Statistics Canada 2009), before starting to plummet at an accelerated speed to around 10% in 2015.

Compared to the nominal share, the real manufacturing share of GDP (shown in Figure 4), the real share of GDP was quite high (around 26%) before 1973, but had the significant drop between 1973 and 1982: between 1973 and 1974, and between 1979 and 1982, the real manufacturing output had micro contraction (see Figure 2), while the real total GDP was more rapidly growing regardless. After 1982, the share has been moving in a range between 11% and 14%, then went on to drop after 2000 to a historical low of around 10%.

- Manufacturing employment

Figure 5. Manufacturing employment, Canada, 1976-2019

Figure 6. Manufacturing employment share, Canada, 1976-2019

Starting from 1976, the manufacturing share in total employment has been in decline continuously from around 19% in 1976 to slightly above 9% in 2019 (a decline of 10 percentage points). In terms of the employment numbers, it's slightly ambiguous: prior to 2000, the trend was moving upward cyclically - from 1994 to 2004, the employment harvested gains, during which it grew from around 1.8 million in 1994 to 2.3 million in 2004. However, the employment endured a sudden collapse after 2004 to a little above 1.7 million in 2015 with no since rebound. Historically, manufacturing was cyclically sensitive (Houseman 2018). Despite this, it didn't see a rebound in employment numbers during the macroeconomic recovery period after the 2009 recession as did in the past, nor did it see any rebound during the same period because of exchange-rate cycles, which we will discuss in later sections. It's noteworthy that the manufacturing employment share is more meaningful than the absolute employment number because it contains the information of the total labour force. In fact, between 1998 and 2014, Canada's working age population grew more than 18%.

- Manufacturing sector of Canada's provinces

We have described the historical data including changes and the trends of the manufacturing sector at the national level - it fell short of expectation especially since the early 2000s. This makes one wonder what it looks like at the provincial level, especially for Ontario and Quebec which together contributed 76.68% of the national manufacturing GDP in 2000, 51.10% and 25.58% respectively (Table 1).

Figure 7. Nominal manufacturing GDP by prov, Canada, 1997-2016

Figure 8. Real manufacturing GDP index by prov., Canada, 1997-2018

As depicted in Figure 7, Ontario's manufacturing nominal GDP hit the peak in 2002 and started to decline. Until 2016, its production was still lower than the peak. Quebec's nominal manufacturing GDP ranks

second nationally, accounting for around 25% of national production in 2016, and Alberta the third, accounting for 11.74%. The real manufacturing GDP of more than half of the provinces slowed down the growth in around 2000, and started to decline in around 2004 (except for B.C, Alberta, Saskatchewan, Manitoba and P.E.I.).

Ontario as the dominant province in national manufacturing got hit especially hard in terms of both nominal and real manufacturing GDP. Additionally, its share of national manufacturing GDP decreased by 5.53 percentage points between 2000 and 2016, and its manufacturing share of its provincial GDP (21.25%), which was the highest among all provinces, also declined the most (-9.96 percentage points), more than the national average (-7.31 percentage points). For other provinces, with regard to share in the national manufacturing GDP, most of them retained their shares, while Alberta was the only one which increased relatively substantively by 4 percentage points and Ontario decreased by 5.53 percentage points as mentioned between 2000 and 2016. Alberta's gains mainly came from manufacturing of petroleum, chemical, metal and machinery products. Even so, it did not prevent Alberta's manufacturing sector losing its share in its GDP. For the manufacturing share in provincial GDP, Quebec (12.71%), Ontario (11.59%), and P.E.I (10.12%) rank the top three as of 2016, while Newfoundland and Labrador (3.97%), Saskatchewan (5.38%) and B.C (6.51%) rank the last.

Country/Province	Share of National Manufacturing GDP (Per Cent)			Share of Provincial GDP (Per Cent)		
	2000	2016	00-16	2000	2016	00-16
Canada	100.00	100.00	0	17.41	10.10	-7.31
Newfoundland and Labrador	0.40	0.62	0.22	5.37	3.97	-1.40
Prince Edward Island	0.20	0.32	0.12	11.13	10.12	-1.01
Nova Scotia	1.40	1.35	-0.05	10.34	6.52	-3.81
New Brunswick	1.52	1.55	0.03	13.74	9.09	-4.65
Quebec	25.58	25.24	-0.34	20.85	12.71	-8.14
Ontario	51.10	45.57	-5.53	21.25	11.59	-9.66
Manitoba	2.23	3.01	0.78	12.65	9.00	-3.64
Saskatchewan	1.29	2.0	0.71	7.06	5.38	-1.67
Alberta	7.74	11.74	4.00	9.91	7.76	-2.15
British Columbia	8.40	8.55	0.15	11.59	6.51	-5.08

Source: Statistics Canada, CANSIM Table 36-10-0402-01, 36100221, and authors' calculations.

Table 1. Share of national manu. GDP, share of provincial GDP by province, Canada, 2000 and 2016.

Similarly to the production, manufacturing employment in most provinces reached the peak in around 2004, and started to plummet. Some rebounded after the 2009 recession such as Alberta, Saskatchewan and P.E.I., while some never did such as Ontario and Quebec. In terms of the manufacturing employment share, most provinces have been on the decline trend to the historical lows. It's noticeable that while the manufacturing employment share of most provinces were below the national average (9.4% in 2016), Quebec and Ontario were slightly above the average.

Figure 9. Manufacturing employment by prov., Canada, 1987-2019

Figure 10. Manufacturing employment share by prov., Canada, 1987-2019

2.2 Is the manufacturing sector in decline?

An OECD study by Pilat et al. (2006) points to the fact that the share of manufacturing in value-added at current prices has slowly declined, as has the share of total employment of the manufacturing sector in Canada. It's true that from numbers, the manufacturing share of GDP or employment has been constantly shrinking. However, a general problem of using the nominal share of the total GDP to infer whether or not the manufacturing sector is in decline is that prices are an important determinant of the share of value-added originating in the manufacturing sector, as well as volumes. Between 1961 and 2005, manufacturing prices rose at an average annual rate of 3.5%, compared with 4% for services. These relative price declines led to decreases in the share of nominal GDP accounted for by manufacturing (Statistics Canada 2009). Meanwhile, because Canada is a relatively small economy compared to the US and over 70% of its exports are sent to the US, Canadian manufacturing prices are affected by exchange-rate cycles of CAD/USD (Statistics Canada 2009), therefore influencing the output. Besides, it can also mean that other sectors underwent faster growth than the manufacturing sector or the result of a society starting to value or demand services like education, healthcare or financial services more than manufactured products. Therefore, only looking at the nominal or real shares of GDP may lead to misunderstandings. Additionally, the decline in the employment numbers or employment share may simply mean the growth of labour productivity in the manufacturing sector, in which case we should verify (in later sections). But if this is the case, the decline in manufacturing employment at least should not cause the stagnation or slowdown of the output. The bottom line is to check if the manufacturing share of GDP or employment dropped more than what is expected to be normal, that is, decline is not a “real decline” if merely caused by labour productivity growth, relative price/valuation change, or relative demand change between manufactured goods and services.

As a result, we recommend putting more emphasis on the real output especially when they endured an abnormal decrease after 2000 to judge whether there's a decline in the manufacturing sector, as well as in our later analysis. As described above, the real output of today is still lower than the year 2000 (the “lost two decades”) with slower recovering pace. Even for the nominal output, it just reached the 2000 levels which were 20 years ago. That being said, the manufacturing share's decline should not have been merely caused by “normal” reasons as stated above. Therefore the decline in numbers can be regarded as “decline” in our judgement.

In summary, as described above in Section 2.1 and 2.2, even though different measures of the manufacturing sector can be indicative of heterogeneous interpretations for the past 60 years, after 2000, almost all of them signified the symptoms of the decline or stagnation in the manufacturing sector, especially the measure of real outputs.

2.3 Manufacturing productivity

In economics, productivity can refer to 1) multi-factor productivity or total factor productivity, which means the aggregate outputs divided by the aggregate inputs, or 2) partial productivity. Partial productivity is the measurement that uses one class of input, such as labour input (labour productivity). In this paper, as our focus is on the output and the employment data in the manufacturing sector, we thereby look at labour productivity which is a measure of real GDP per hour worked (Statistics Canada 2019).

Figure 11. Labour productivity, manufacturing and business sector.

Figure 12. Labour productivity growth, manufacturing vs business sector.

As depicted in Figure 7, labour productivity of the manufacturing sector has historically outpaced that of the business sector for the past 60 years. For example, from 1961 to 2017, the manufacturing labour productivity grew by 450%, while the business sector by less than 300%. Regarding the decade-wise data, in the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s, manufacturing productivity growth rate was significantly higher than the

business sector, and the average manufacturing productivity growth rate before 2000 was at around 3% level. Though dropping to a historically low level of around 1.3%-ish after 2000, the manufacturing sector still outperformed the average business sector. We also notice that while the manufacturing labour productivity significantly slowed down after 2000, the business sector (which includes manufacturing) lost momentum.

NAICS Codes	Labour Productivity Growth		Change in Hours Worked Share	
	Compound Annual Growth Rate (G _t)	Difference with Business Sector (G _t - 1.99)	Percentage Point	Per Cent
Business sector	1.99	0.00	0.00	0.00
Crop and animal production	3.80	1.82	-11.68	-83.47
Forestry and logging	3.06	1.08	-1.48	-82.14
Fishing, hunting and trapping	1.93	-0.05	-0.54	-82.77
Support activities for agriculture and forestry	1.01	-0.97	0.04	25.60
Mining and oil and gas extraction	0.40	-1.58	0.53	34.75
Utilities	1.76	-0.22	0.20	30.94
Construction	1.02	-0.96	1.03	10.10
Manufacturing	2.81	0.83	-13.50	-51.00
Wholesale trade	2.86	0.88	1.66	35.42
Retail trade	2.55	0.56	0.77	6.39
Transportation and warehousing	2.44	0.45	-0.50	-7.37
Information and cultural industries	3.38	1.39	0.82	50.35
Finance, insurance, real estate and renting and leasing	1.10	-0.88	4.45	86.19
Professional, scientific and technical services	0.79	-1.20	6.46	373.68
Administrative and support, waste management and remediation services	-0.59	-2.57	5.68	1,014.71
Educational services (except universities)
Health care and social assistance (except hospitals)	-0.03	-2.01	3.22	294.28
Arts, entertainment and recreation	-0.41	-2.40	1.45	414.80
Accommodation and food services	-0.23	-2.21	2.58	54.92
Other services (except public administration)	1.04	-0.95	-1.19	-20.23

Note: Labour productivity is defined as real GDP per hour worked.

Source: CSLS calculations based on Statistics Canada data. CANSIM tables 383-0032 and 383-0021.

Table 2. Labour productivity growth and hours worked by industry, Canada, per cent, 1961-2011 (Table taken from CSLS)

As shown in Figure 9, the compound annual labour productivity of the manufacturing sector between 1961 and 2011 was 2.81%, lower than crop and animal production (3.8%); information and cultural industries (3.38%); forestry and logging (3.06%); and slightly lower than whole trade (2.86), but higher than retail trade (2.55%); transportation (2.44%); utilities (1.76%); finance (1.1%); construction (1.02%); professional, scientific and technical services (0.79%); mining and oil/gas extraction (0.4%); and health care and social assistance (-0.03%).

In summary, labour productivity in the manufacturing sector has been leading the overall labour productivity growth in Canada for the past 60 years by remarkably exceeding the average business sector, as well as most of the major sectors such as finance, healthcare or construction. By definition, if the labour productivity growth rate is higher than the growth rate of total output, then part of the decline of the employment can be explained by labour productivity. Any other residual if any requires other explanation.

Also, the growth of labour productivity by itself should not suppress output growth which we have seen in Section 2.1. We will analyze these in further detail in later sections.

2.4 What has replaced the manufacturing share of total employment or output?

- Shifts in nominal output share

NAICS Codes	Share of Total (Per Cent)				Absolute Change (Percentage Points)			Relative Change (Per Cent)		
	1961	1976	1987	2011	61-11	76-11	87-11	61-11	76-11	87-11
All industries	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Primary industries</i>	10.55	10.43	7.97	10.16	-0.39	-0.26	2.19	-3.68	-2.52	27.47
Crop and animal production [111, 112]	4.55	3.62	2.00	1.35	-3.21	-2.27	-0.65	-70.44	-62.80	-32.73
Forestry and logging [113]	1.31	0.86	0.66	0.22	-1.08	-0.63	-0.44	-82.78	-73.76	-66.09
Fishing, hunting and trapping [114]	0.22	0.16	0.22	0.07	-0.15	-0.09	-0.15	-68.66	-55.76	-67.73
Support activities for agriculture and forestry [115]	0.22	0.14	-0.08	-37.37
Mining and oil and gas extraction [21]	4.47	5.79	4.87	8.39	3.92	2.59	3.51	87.61	44.75	72.05
<i>Secondary industries</i>	32.20	28.45	27.46	20.14	-12.06	-8.31	-7.32	-37.47	-29.21	-26.67
Utilities [22]	2.30	2.08	3.17	2.38	0.08	0.29	-0.79	3.35	14.08	-25.04
Construction [23]	7.47	8.34	6.49	7.19	-0.28	-1.15	0.70	-3.77	-13.82	10.81
Manufacturing [31, 32, 33]	22.43	18.02	17.80	10.57	-11.86	-7.45	-7.23	-52.87	-41.34	-40.62
<i>Tertiary industries</i>	57.25	61.13	64.57	69.70	12.45	8.57	5.13	21.75	14.02	7.95
Wholesale trade [41]	4.67	4.85	5.12	5.22	0.55	0.37	0.10	11.81	7.66	1.91
Retail trade [44, 45]	7.36	6.55	6.33	5.10	-2.26	-1.45	-1.23	-30.70	-22.11	-19.47
Transportation and warehousing [48, 49]	6.99	5.62	5.34	4.12	-2.87	-1.50	-1.22	-41.07	-26.75	-22.83
Information and cultural industries [51]	3.29	3.26	3.14	3.19	-0.09	-0.07	0.06	-2.83	-2.01	1.76
Finance, insurance, real estate and rental and leasing [52, 53, 55]	14.27	13.55	17.16	19.20	4.93	5.65	2.04	34.53	41.70	11.88
Professional and business services (PBS)	1.88	3.08	4.38	8.32	6.45	5.25	3.95	343.45	170.49	90.25
Professional, scientific and technical services [54]	1.42	1.91	2.69	5.60	4.18	3.69	2.91	294.54	193.02	108.24
Administrative and support, waste management and remediation services [56]	0.46	1.17	1.68	2.72	2.26	1.56	1.04	495.48	133.51	61.51
Educational services [61]	3.31	6.03	5.26	5.35	2.04	-0.68	0.09	61.59	-11.30	1.77
Health care and social assistance [62]	3.41	5.21	6.07	7.07	3.66	1.85	1.00	107.13	35.54	16.45
Arts, entertainment and recreation [71]	0.42	0.80	0.75	0.77	0.35	-0.03	0.02	82.97	-3.61	2.31
Accommodation and food services [72]	2.34	2.73	2.46	2.02	-0.31	-0.70	-0.44	-13.42	-25.80	-17.76
Other services (except public administration) [81]	2.76	2.33	1.87	2.05	-0.72	-0.29	0.18	-25.91	-12.24	9.72
Public administration [91]	6.56	7.12	6.70	7.29	0.73	0.17	0.59	11.18	2.35	8.82

Source: CSLS calculations based on Statistics Canada data. CANSIM tables 379-0023 (1961, 1976 and 1987) and 379-0029 (2011).

Table 2. Share of nominal GDP by industry by period, Canada, 1961-2011 (table from CSLS)

As shown in Table 2 above, between 1961 to 2011, the manufacturing output as a share of nominal GDP decreased from 22.43% to 10.57% by 11.86 percentage points, during which from 1987 to 2011, the manufacturing output as a share of GDP declined from 17.80% to 10.57% by 7.43 percentage points. Between 1961 and 2011, sectors with loss in share of GDP include crop and animal production (-3.21 percentage points); transportation and warehousing (-2.87 percentage points); and retail trade (-2.26 percentage points). Sectors with the biggest gains are professional and business services (+6.45 percentage points); finance and real estate (+4.93 percentage points); mining, oil and gas extraction (+3.92 percentage points); health care and social assistance (+3.66 percentage points); educational services (+2.04 percentage points).

- Shifts in the employment share

NAICS Codes	Share of Total (Per Cent)			Absolute Change (Percentage Points)	
	1976	2000	2019	76-19	00-19
Total, all industries	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
Goods-producing sector	34.58	25.81	20.76	-13.82	-5.05
Agriculture	4.76	2.52	1.51	-3.25	-1.01
Forestry, fishing, mining, quarrying, oil and gas	2.61	1.85	1.74	-0.87	-0.11
Utilities	1.13	0.78	0.73	-0.40	-0.05
Construction	6.99	5.47	7.68	0.69	2.21
Manufacturing	19.09	15.19	9.09	-10.00	-6.10
Services-producing sector	65.42	74.19	79.24	13.82	5.05
Wholesale and retail trade	16.12	15.58	14.91	-1.21	-0.67
Transportation and warehousing	5.78	5.24	5.45	-0.33	0.21
Finance, insurance, real estate, rental and leasing	5.40	5.81	6.34	0.95	0.53
Professional, scientific and technical services	2.59	6.34	8.16	5.57	1.82
Business, building and other support services	1.66	3.60	4.07	2.42	0.47
Educational services	6.94	6.57	7.19	0.25	0.62
Health care and social assistance	8.14	10.28	13.07	4.92	2.79
Information, culture and recreation	3.56	4.52	4.06	0.50	-0.46
Accommodation and food services	4.24	6.37	6.38	2.14	0.01
Other services (except public administration)	4.38	4.63	4.29	-0.09	-0.34
Public administration	6.62	5.25	5.31	-1.30	0.07

Source: Statistics Canada, CANSIM Table 14-10-0023-01, and authors' calculations.

Table 3. Share of employment by industry by period, Canada, 1976-2019

The manufacturing share in total employment dropped from 19.09% in 1976 to 9.09% in 2019, by 10.00 percentage points, in which between 2000 and 2019, a decrease of 6.10 percentage points was observed. Between 1976 and 2019, a whopping 13.82 percentage points shifted from goods-producing sector to services-producing sector, and sectors which had gains in the share of employment were professional, scientific and technical services (+5.57 percentage points); health care and social assistance (+4.92 percentage points); business, building and other support services (+2.42 percentage points); and accommodation and food services (+2.14 percentage points). The losing sectors besides the manufacturing sector were agriculture (-3.25 percentage points); public administration (-1.30 percentage points); and wholesale and retail trade (-1.21 percentage points). Also notice that when manufacturing employment share endured rapid decrease post 2000, sectors which filled the gap were healthcare and social assistance; and professional, scientific and technical services. On the surface, the manufacturing loss in the share of total employment was filled by jobs such as professional, healthcare and business. The aggregate labour market effects may be positive. However, the displaced workers may suffer because of career setbacks, and income inequality among workers in different sectors may get larger, which depends on the wage growth situations in these sectors. In other words, those sectors that filled the gap may not be because displaced manufacturing workers filled in, rather it can be a structural shift due to economic development. Low share of goods-producing jobs may suppress the goods output which may negatively impact the export capacity since goods are the major portion of Canadian exports. We will have more analysis in Section 4.

Figure 13. Labour participation rate, Canada, 1976-2019.

We would like to point out that between 2000 and 2019, the labour participation rate in Canada generally ran inside a stable range (between 65% and 68%). Supposedly the decline in the share of manufacturing employment did not associate with a decline in the labour participation.

2.5 Change within the manufacturing sector

NAICS Codes	GDP Share (Per Cent)			Abs. Change (Percentage Points)		Hours Worked Share (Per Cent)			Abs. Change (Percentage Points)	
	1976	2000	2015	76-15	00-15	1976	2000	2015	76-15	00-15
Manufacturing	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
Food manufacturing	11.13	8.19	12.05	0.92	3.85	11.14	9.28	13.45	2.31	4.17
Beverage and tobacco product manufacturing	3.65	2.62	3.34	-0.31	0.72	2.43	1.24	2.39	-0.04	1.15
Textile and textile product mills	1.96	1.45	0.64	-1.32	-0.81	2.75	2.38	1.14	-1.62	-1.24
Clothing, Leather and allied product manufacturing	4.72	2.41	0.59	-4.13	-1.82	8.74	5.09	1.57	-7.17	-3.52
Wood product manufacturing	5.68	6.43	4.51	-1.17	-1.91	7.68	7.67	6.11	-1.57	-1.56
Paper manufacturing	8.97	7.23	4.32	-4.65	-2.91	7.17	5.50	3.71	-3.47	-1.79
Printing and related support activities	2.57	2.87	2.15	-0.42	-0.71	2.88	3.91	3.29	0.41	-0.62
Petroleum and coal products manufacturing	1.78	1.41	7.51	5.73	6.10	0.42	0.35	0.90	0.48	0.55
Chemical manufacturing	6.93	7.17	10.01	3.08	2.84	4.83	4.12	5.80	0.97	1.68
Plastics and rubber products manufacturing	2.96	4.64	5.16	2.20	0.52	3.23	6.03	6.59	3.36	0.56
Non-metallic mineral product manufacturing	3.90	2.30	3.06	-0.85	0.76	3.18	2.43	3.59	0.41	1.17
Primary metal manufacturing	7.45	6.13	5.72	-1.73	-0.42	6.24	4.34	4.21	-2.03	-0.13
Fabricated metal product manufacturing	7.23	6.56	7.73	0.50	1.17	7.22	9.22	10.56	3.34	1.33
Machinery manufacturing	5.74	6.46	7.48	1.74	1.02	6.29	7.83	9.16	2.87	1.33
Computer and electronic product manufacturing	4.55	6.75	3.17	-1.37	-3.58	5.30	6.63	3.38	-1.92	-3.25
Electrical equipment, appliance and component manufacturing	4.09	2.29	1.86	-2.23	-0.42	4.48	2.66	2.19	-2.28	-0.47
Transportation equipment manufacturing	13.04	20.67	16.13	3.09	-4.54	10.24	13.02	13.38	3.13	0.36
Furniture and related product manufacturing	1.76	2.74	2.36	0.60	-0.39	3.05	5.40	4.77	1.72	-0.63

Source: Statistics Canada, CANSIM Table 36-10-0217-01, and authors' calculations.

Table 4. Share of GDP and employment within the manufacturing sector, Canada, 1976-2015

In 1976, the top five manufacturing sub-sectors in terms of GDP share were transportation equipment (13.04%), food (11.13%), paper (8.97%), primary metal (7.45%) and fabricated metal product (7.23%). In 2015, the top five are transportation equipment (16.13%), food (12.05%), chemical (10.01%), fabricated metal product (7.73%), and petroleum and coal products (7.51%). Between 1976 and 2015, the winners were petroleum and coal products (+5.73 percentage points), transportation (+3.09 percentage points), and

chemical (+3.08 percentage points). The losers were paper (-4.65 percentage points); clothing, leather and allied product (-4.13 percentage points); and electrical equipment, appliance and component manufacturing (-2.23 percentage points).

With regard to employment share (measured by share of hours worked share, supposedly employees in each industry work similar hours per person per week), the top five sub-sectors in 1976 were food (11.14%); transportation equipment (10.24%); clothing, leather and allied products (8.74%); wood products (7.68%); and fabricated metal products (7.22%). In 2015, the top five were food (13.45%); transportation equipment (13.38%); fabricated metal products (10.56%); machinery (9.16%); and plastics and rubber products (6.59%). Between 1976 and 2015, the winners were plastics and rubber products (+3.36 percentage points); fabricated metal products (+3.34 percentage points); and transportation equipment (+3.13 percentage points). The losers were clothing, leather and allied products (-7.17 percentage points); paper (-3.47 percentage points); and electrical equipment, appliance and component (-2.28 percentage points).

Overall, the major part of Canada's manufacturing output comes increasingly from manufacturing of food and natural resource related products, which account for a total of over 60% of the entire manufacturing GDP in 2015. Canada has been losing low value added manufacturing such as clothing, paper and wood products. Conversely, some mid to high value added manufacturing such as computers, electrical equipment and transportation, together have lost more than 8 percentage points since 2000.

Similar to output share, in 2015, around 60% of the hours worked fell into manufacturing of food and natural resource related products. There are some interesting findings: since 2000, sub-sectors with biggest loss include clothing and computer assembling; these low-skilled or labour intensive sectors have been in the process of relocating out of Canada. The sub-sector of petroleum and coal products manufacturing which is more capital intensive produced 7.51% of total manufacturing output, but only hires 0.9% of total manufacturing employment. Sub-sectors which can be more automated such as food, beverage and tobacco kept their output and employment shares. Sub-sectors which align with Canada's endowments such as technology (transportation equipment, machinery) or natural resources (chemical, plastics, metallics) also kept their relative employment share.

Figure 14. Nominal GDP, within the manufacturing sector, Canada.

Figure 15. Real GDP, within the manufacturing sector, Canada.

By analyzing the output levels of sub-sectors of the manufacturing sector, whether measured by the nominal or real terms, almost all of them experienced a different degree of growth before the year 2000. The best performing categories (for illustrative purposes, we combined similar sub-sectors into categories) were the manufacturing products of transportation; petroleum, chemical and plastics; wood and paper; metal and minerals; and food, beverage and tobacco. After 2000, nominal output of most categories declined or significantly slowed down, with only two exceptions: 1. food, beverage and tobacco; and 2. petroleum, chemical and plastics. However, even these two winners, measured in real terms, performed quite poorly with the latter declined. Some categories also declined hard during the recession caused by the 2008 financial crisis such as transportation; and metal and mineral products, but both had a relatively strong rebound thereafter.

NAICS Codes	GDP Share (Per Cent)			Abs. Change (Percentage Points)	
	1976	2000	2015	76-15	00-15
Manufacturing	16.80	17.39	9.97	-6.83	-7.42
Food; Beverage and tobacco product manufacturing	2.48	1.88	1.53	-0.95	-0.35
Textile; Clothing, Leather and allied product manufacturing	1.12	0.67	0.12	-1	-0.55
Wood product; Paper; Printing and related support manufacturing	2.89	2.87	1.10	-1.79	-1.77
Petroleum and coal products; Chemical; Plastics and rubber products manufacturing	1.96	2.30	2.26	0.3	-0.04
Non-metallic mineral; Primary metal; Fabricated metal products	3.12	2.61	1.65	-1.47	-0.96
Machinery manufacturing	0.96	1.12	0.75	-0.21	-0.37
Computer and electronic product manufacturing	0.76	1.17	0.32	-0.44	-0.85
Electrical equipment, appliance and component manufacturing	0.69	0.40	0.19	-0.5	-0.21
Transportation equipment manufacturing	2.19	3.59	1.61	-0.58	-1.98
Furniture and related product manufacturing	0.30	0.48	0.24	-0.06	-0.24

Source: Statistics Canada, CANSIM Table 36-10-0217-01, OECD and authors' calculations.

Table 5. Nominal share of total GDP, manufacturing sub-sectors, Canada, 1976-2015.

Table 5 shows the nominal share of total GDP for the combined categories of manufacturing sub-sectors and their changes in periods 1976-2015 and 2000-2015, respectively. As the total manufacturing output as a share of GDP fell from around 17% in 1976 or 2000 to only 9.97% in 2015, all categories unsurprisingly endured a decline during 1976-2015 or 2000-2015 periods. Only the category of petroleum, chemical and plastics had a marginal decline between 2000 and 2015. Transportation equipment manufacturing had the biggest loss (-1.98 percentage points), and manufacturing of wood, paper and printing products came second (-1.77 percentage points), then metal and mineral related products (-0.96 percentage points).

2.6 Comparison of Canada and the world

- **Canada and other major countries**

Figure 16. Manufacturing share of GDP, OECD countries (from World Bank) Figure 17. Manufacturing share of GDP by Country (from RBC).

It is helpful to look at the cross-country data to get perspective of Canada’s position in a broader context. We present the manufacturing sectors in major OECD countries and China. As shown in Figure 16, a majority of developed countries in the OECD experienced a decline in the manufacturing share of nominal GDP, including the US, Canada, France, the UK, and Australia. In 2018, the manufacturing shares of the US, Canada, France, the US were around 10%, with Australia approximately 6%. The numbers of Japan, Germany and Mexico were quite stable in the past two decades, with Japan at 20.7%, Germany 20.4% and Mexico at 17.3% in 2018. South Korea and China were high above all major countries with 27% and 29.4%, respectively. Comparing levels in 2010 to 1990, countries such as Germany, Mexico, South Korea and China had only a minor decrease in manufacturing output share of their GDP.

As seen from Figure 17, the manufacturing output share of industrializing developing countries such as Mexico, and especially China were much more stable than developed countries. Their GDP growth rates were also higher, which means the global manufacturing output share has been shifting towards developing countries. In fact, as shown in Figure 18, while the manufacturing output of most developed countries had a slower growth, between 1990 and 2018, the manufacturing output of China (in current US dollars) grew

by more than 2600% to almost double of the size of the US in 2018. South Korea also experienced growth by over 600%, and Mexico over 400%. Comparatively, developed countries conversely grew significantly slower - Canada (85%), the US (120%), Japan (20%), Germany (80%), France (30%), and the UK (38%). Notably, China's output of 2018 was almost the combined total of all listed developed countries (\$4.0 trillion v.s. \$5.4 trillion). Further to this, data from 2019 shows that China still far outpaced industrialized countries in terms of the growth rate in almost all manufacturing sub-sectors as of 2019 (Figure 15).

Figure 18. Manufacturing output, major countries, 1990-2018.

Figure 19. Growth rate of manu. sub-sectors, Q3, 2019 (from UN).

Figure 20. Manufacturing share of employment, OECD countries

Figure 21. Manufacturing employment, OECD countries

On the employment front, most major OECD countries saw a constant decline of the manufacturing employment share. Even South Korea, with its robust pre-1990 expansion, has shrank ever since. Countries such as the US, the UK, Canada, Australia, and France reached distinguishably low levels between 9% to 11% in around the year 2010. Traditional manufacturing intensive countries such as Japan, Germany and Italy - though also declining - were able to maintain their manufacturing employment share above 16% in 2009. With regard to manufacturing employment, Canada did perform fairly well before 2000 by keeping the employment number at a stable level before a deep drop of 20% thereafter. The same situation applies to the US which lost over 30% of its manufacturing jobs since 2000. France, the UK, and Australia’s employment numbers have consistently declined since the 1970s. On the other hand, Germany, Italy and South Korea’s employment numbers were quite stable. Japan also had a dramatic decline, with over 25% of loss in manufacturing employment since 2000. However, as Benedetto (2018) pointed out, between 1998 and 2014, the working age population of Japan and Germany shrank by 9% and 4.8%, while the US and Canada’s grew by more than 16% and 18% respectively.

- **Canada and the United States**

The economies of Canada and the US have been highly integrated which was especially evident since the beginning of NAFTA in 1994. Both countries experienced common economic shocks throughout the recent history, and the relative performance of the business sectors in the two countries was remarkably similar (Statistics Canada 2009) as shown in Figure 23. The value of Canada’s total merchandise trade (exports plus imports) with the US accounts for 64.0% of its total merchandise trade with the world (Statistics Canada 2017).

Figure 22. Manufacturing nominal gross domestic product by industry, Canada and US (figures from Statistics Canada, 2017)

In terms of the manufacturing output, the manufacturing output share of GDP in the US has contracted since the 1950s to 11.1% as of 2018, slightly above Canada of 10.3% in 2015.

Figure 23. Real manufacturing output after 2000, Canada vs the US (figure from Statistics Canada, 2017)

As introduced in Section 2.1, the real manufacturing GDP in Canada kept pace with the business sector before 2000, which is the same thing that happened to the US manufacturing. However, the real manufacturing output of Canada started to diverge from the business sector, as well as from its US counterpart. The reason for this was that there was no similar momentum from the computer and electronics industry in Canada, as in the US (Statistics Canada 2017). The US manufacturing sector has not been positive though - since the 1980s, the US manufacturing output was driven by a single sector, the computer and electronics industry (13% of entire manufacturing output). Other US manufacturing sectors have grown much slower, which were about 45% of the business sector average between 1979 and 2000, and only 12% in the 2000s (Houseman 2018). With that said, without the computer and electronics industry, the manufacturing output growth of the US in the 2000s would have been similar to Canada (see Table 6).

Average contribution to manufacturing growth

	2000 to 2007			2008 to 2009			2010 to 2016		
	Canada	U.S.	Difference	Canada	U.S.	Difference	Canada	U.S.	Difference
	percentage points								
Total manufacturing (growth)	0.7	3.1	-2.4	-9.6	-5.3	-4.3	1.9	1.5	0.4
Durable goods	0.4	2.6	-2.2	-7.2	-4.3	-2.9	1.3	1.9	-0.6
Wood products	0.2	0.0	0.2	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	0.3	0.0	0.3
Non-metallic minerals	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.3	-0.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
Primary metals	0.1	-0.1	0.2	-1.2	0.0	-1.2	0.2	0.2	0.0
Fabricated metals	0.2	0.1	0.1	-0.9	-1.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	-0.1
Machinery	0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.7	-0.7	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0
Computers and electronics	-0.2	2.0	-2.2	-0.3	0.8	-1.1	-0.1	0.5	-0.6
Electrical equipment	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
Transportation equipment	-0.1	0.4	-0.5	-2.6	-2.4	-0.2	0.7	0.9	-0.2
Furniture	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.4	-0.3	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
Miscellaneous manufacturing	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.2	0.2	-0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0
Non-durable goods	0.3	0.5	-0.2	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	0.6	-0.5	1.1
Food and beverage	0.1	0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.2	-0.2	0.3	-0.3	0.6
Textiles	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
Clothing	0.0	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
Paper	0.0	-0.1	0.1	-0.6	-0.1	-0.5	0.0	-0.1	0.1
Printing	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
Petroleum	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.2	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
Chemicals	0.1	0.4	-0.3	-0.6	-0.5	-0.1	0.3	-0.1	0.4
Plastics and rubber	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	0.2	0.0	0.2

Notes: Components may not sum to totals due to rounding. Constant dollar data used to provide growth rates in the Tornqvist transformation are available up to 2016. Current dollar data used to provide the weights of the industrial sectors in the total manufacturing sector is available up to 2013. The most recent weights available, 2013, are thus used to calculate the contributions to growth for the years 2014 to 2016.

Sources: Statistics Canada, CANSIM tables 383-0032 and 379-0031; U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis; and authors' calculations.

Table 6. Average contribution to manufacturing growth, Canada and U.S., 2000-2017. (table from Statistics Canada, 2017)

Figure 24. Manufacturing employment, Canada vs US

Figure 25. Manufacturing employment share, Canada vs U.S.

On the employment front, between the 1970s and early 2000s, manufacturing employment numbers of both Canada and the US were quite stable, with Canada having a cyclical increase (we will further analyze this in Section 3). However, both suffered from a dramatic decrease in the 2000s, with the US losing over 5 million (30%+) manufacturing jobs. Regarding the manufacturing employment share, both countries generally followed a declining trend to the historically low 10%, which is comparable to the lowest levels in developed countries (Figure 25).

3. The Causes of the Decline

As explained in Section 2.6, the economies of Canada and the US are highly integrated with more than 70% of Canada's exports going to the US. The manufacturing sectors of the two economies have notably similar sector structures, sub-sector growth rates (except for the computer and electronics industry), historical trends, and levels of current output and employment shares. Arguably, booms and busts that one country's manufacturing sector has had, should be experienced by the other too; because of similar exposure to international trade, macroeconomic cycles, technological change, labour market disruptions, and monetary policies. The US has significantly more research on manufacturing decline compared to Canada, but this analysis can also apply to Canada. Therefore, we will cross analyze US cases when it helps to explain the Canadian phenomenon. The emphasis will be the sudden decline and divergence from the business sector since 2000, because the manufacturing output had grown robustly prior to 2000. We will look at both output and employment sides.

3.1 Decline of manufacturing output or employment shares

By definition, the decline in output share is due to the relative decrease of the manufacturing output from other sectors' output, and the decline in employment share is due to the relative decrease of manufacturing employment compared to other sector employment. As described in Section 2.2, the manufacturing share of the nominal total GDP in Canada followed a downward trend from 1961 to 1992, which was mostly because of the price decrease of manufactured goods (Statistics Canada 2009). Capeluck (2015) found that between 1961 and 2000, the above-average labour productivity growth rate in the manufacturing sector can explain a significant portion of the employment share decline, but not the period after 2000. Hirshhorn (2013) argued that stronger final demand for services could be a potential driver of the decline in manufacturing's output and then the decline in employment share in Canada, though there is sparse empirical research on this. Outsourcing contracts to service sectors from manufacturing sectors can also impact the decreasing output or employment shares. Baldwin and Macdonald (2009) claimed that "when manufacturers move from employing staff (whether it be for payroll, accounting, janitorial services or production) to contracting with outside firms, employment in manufacturing necessarily decreases while services employment rises", yet this kind of effect was "small" (Capeluck 2015). Other factors such as international trade and offshoring (Jenkins 2008, Baldwin and Macdonald 2009), appreciation of CAD/USD (Macklem 2013), the "Dutch disease" (Beine et al. 2012), weakening global competitiveness of Canadian products (Capeluck 2015), and relative weaker US demand from either weaker domestic growth or shifting demand away from Canada to Asia (Sharpe 2014) all impair the manufacturing share, through output.

However, apart from the research above about the decline in employment and output shares, we could not conclude if its overall impact is negative, when we assess the past 60 years together. After all, even if the output share declined, the output growth from the early 1960s until the late 1990s had been rather robust (real output kept pace with the business sector), and the manufacturing employment had been moving upward cyclically.

Consequently, we argue that there should be less concern about the decrease of shares in economic impact over the period between 1961 and 2000. What should be more concerning is the period after the early 2000s, in which the real output suddenly stagnated and declined, and the employment collapsed without ever rebounding. In other words, had the real output and employment kept the same growth rate as before 2000, the drop in their shares may not be so dramatic. In the next subsections, we will try to explain the real output and employment decline after 2000.

3.2 Decline of the manufacturing employment

- Theoretical model

Capeluck (2015) argued that employment growth in any industry is positively related to real output growth (the demand channel) and negatively related to labour productivity growth (the labour productivity channel), *ceteris paribus*. That is, the growth rate of employment (L) approximately equals the output growth rate (Y) minus the labour productivity growth rate (P):

$$\Delta L/L \approx \Delta Y/Y - \Delta P/P *$$

*see Appendix 1 for proof.

This is consistent with the historical data shown in Table 7. For example, between 2001 and 2015, the hours worked (employment) in the manufacturing sector decreased by 1.82% annually, the manufacturing labour productivity growth was 1.24%, and real manufacturing GDP growth rate was -0.6% (-1.82% equals approximately -0.6% minus 1.24%). Between 1961 and 2000, employment growth rate was 0.77%, which is approximately 4.19% minus 3.39%. The calculations of sub-sectors show similar results.

By definition, labour productivity equals real GDP divided by hours worked. The labour productivity is determined by human capital, physical capital and technological progress, not by hours worked or real output. Real output should be determined by the equilibrium of supply and demand. There was little evidence that Canadian manufacturing sector endured a supply shock starting in the early 2000s, given the

fact that there was slack in the workforce of the manufacturing sector (manufacturing workers got laid off), and arguably cheaper cost of inputs thanks to the growing trade liberalization. Therefore, the real output in this scenario should then be determined by the demand for Canadian manufactured goods, which consists of domestic and foreign ones, not hours worked. Consequently, labour productivity and real output can be treated as exogenous to hours worked, and these two factors working together will determine the hours worked (employment).

NAICS Codes	Labour Productivity Compound Annual Growth Rate (Per Cent)		Real GDP Compound Annual Growth Rate (Per Cent)		Hours worked Compound Annual Growth Rate (Per Cent)	
	61-00	01-15	61-00	01-15	61-00	01-15
Manufacturing	3.39	1.24	4.19	-0.60	0.77	-1.82
Food manufacturing	2.64	0.83	2.28	1.21	-0.35	0.37
Beverage and tobacco product manufacturing	3.11	-3.93	1.54	-1.21	-1.52	2.83
Textile and textile product mills	3.68	1.23	3.34	-5.66	-0.33	-6.80
Clothing, Leather and allied product manufacturing	2.82	1.57	1.55	-8.20	-1.23	-9.62
Wood product manufacturing	3.51	4.07	4.35	0.63	0.82	-3.31
Paper manufacturing	2.47	2.71	2.56	-2.01	0.09	-4.60
Printing and related support activities	0.80	0.84	2.26	-3.14	1.45	-3.94
Petroleum and coal products manufacturing	3.90	-3.65	3.80	-0.82	-0.10	2.93
Chemical manufacturing	4.78	-0.67	5.03	-0.40	0.24	0.27
Plastics and rubber products manufacturing	3.44	1.65	7.08	0.18	3.53	-1.44
Non-metallic mineral product manufacturing	2.61	-0.35	2.63	0.24	0.02	0.59
Primary metal manufacturing	3.36	0.93	3.23	-0.15	-0.12	-1.07
Fabricated metal product manufacturing	2.30	0.72	4.22	-0.26	1.87	-0.98
Machinery manufacturing	2.53	1.24	4.76	0.35	2.17	-0.88
Computer and electronic product manufacturing	7.30	1.15	8.85	-3.60	1.44	-4.69
Electrical equipment, appliance and component manufacturing	3.81	0.55	3.37	-2.74	-0.43	-3.27
Transportation equipment manufacturing	4.81	1.41	7.09	-0.04	2.18	-1.43
Furniture and related product manufacturing	2.51	-0.22	5.17	-3.33	2.59	-3.11

Source: Statistics Canada, CANSIM Table 36-10-0217-01, and authors' calculations.

Table 7. Compound annual growth rate of labour productivity, real GDP and hours worked, manufacturing sector, Canada.

- Is productivity growth to blame?

There is a widely held opinion attributing the loss of manufacturing jobs to productivity growth. For example, an economics professor at Harvard, Lawrence Katz, claimed that “over the long haul, clearly automation’s been much more important (on employment loss)—it’s not even close” (New York Times 2016). The former Bank of Canada Governor Stephen Poloz had a similar view, “new technologies, automation and robotics in Canadian factories are allowing for higher productivity and output with fewer workers” (Bank of Canada 2016).

This argument makes sense, since there has been increasing output per-worker and more work done by robots or automation, resulting in less workers. However, this is based on the assumption that labour

productivity growth is higher than the output growth, and it can further deduce that labour productivity growth should have been much faster after the 2000s than before (if the output driven by the demand did not decline, so that it can explain the employment decline or collapse during the 2000s). Conversely, by looking at Table 7, we found this is not the case. The compounded annual labour productivity growth rate (1.24%) between 2001 and 2015 is significantly slower than that (3.39%) between 1961 and 2000 for the Canadian manufacturing sector and almost all its sub-sectors.

The conclusion is clear now: before 2000, the annual manufacturing labour productivity growth rate was quite fast, yet the real output growth was even faster, which resulted in a positive employment growth rate. However after 2000, labour productivity growth significantly slowed down and the real output growth even turned negative, as a result, employment inevitably decreased. Therefore, after 2000, productivity growth should not be regarded as the primary factor driving the collapse of manufacturing employment, but the negative real output growth should. In other words, if the real output growth would have grown faster than the labour productivity growth like before, the employment would not have dropped. Capeluck (2015) also pointed out that the above-average manufacturing labour productivity growth can only explain the employment share decline between 1961 and 2000, while after 2000, it was driven by the demand channel (output). Baldwin and Macdonald (2009) also noticed that relative labour productivity in manufacturing which hardly changed from 2000 to 2011 cannot be used to explain the employment decline.

Compared to the US, as seen on Table 6, two-thirds of the US manufacturing output growth from 2000 to 2007 was made up by a single industry—computer and electronics industry, without which the US manufacturing output growth would have slowed down to the same rate as Canada. However, Houseman (2018) found that the US computer industry actually had skewed statistics, because the statistics agencies adjusted the price deflator for quality adjustment significantly, when the industry actually had declining real output. The rapid labour productivity growth of the computer industry largely reflects R&D effects rather than automation progress, which has been in this industry for many years, with the locus of production continuously shifting to Asia. Houseman (2018) argues that productivity growth, necessary for the living standard improvement, does not by itself necessarily cause less employment (unless demand is limited) apart from the falling prices, nor can it cause a real output decline, because lower prices will increase demand. Autor, Dorn and Hanson (2015) found that the manufacturing or non-manufacturing sectors of regional labour markets in the US between 1980 and 2007 with more routine manual tasks that were prone to being replaced by automation, did not have a net decline in employment. Surprisingly, they found that the effects of automation on manufacturing which were notable during the 1980s, greatly subsided in the 2000s, while the effects of automation in the non-manufacturing sector accelerated over the same period. Acemoglu and Restrepo (2017) claimed that the adoption of robots could have large negative

effects on employment and wages in the future. However, currently there is limited adoption of industrial robots, so it explains little about the precipitous decline in employment. The industrial robot density in the US and Canada is around 200 per 10,000 workers which is substantially lower than Singapore, Korea, Germany and Japan who all endured much less manufacturing employment loss (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Robot density in the manufacturing sector by country, 2018

To summarize, labour productivity growth explains little about the decline of employment during the 2000s, while decline of the real output does. The question now becomes, why did real output decline? We will investigate this in the next sub-section.

3.3 Decline of manufacturing output

- Theoretical model

Capeluck (2015) argued that real output growth is determined by a large number of underlying dynamic causes. For instance, real output growth is affected by changes in demand condition (both foreign and domestic) and changes in international competitiveness linked to real exchange rates, input costs, tax rates and transportation costs, among other things.

As previously stated, the manufacturing output is determined by the equilibrium of supply and demand. There is no evidence that the decline of the Canadian manufacturing was caused by a supply shock such as labour shortage or the increasing cost of inputs during the 2000s. Thus, the decline was mostly determined by a demand shock. Also, the aggregate demand for the manufactured goods within Canada should equal the aggregate supply. Therefore, we can get:

$$Y_m + M_m = C_m + X_m$$

or

$$Y_m = C_m + (X_m - M_m)$$

where Y_m is domestic manufacturing output, M_m is the imports of manufactured goods, C_m is the domestic consumption of manufactured goods, X_m is the exports of manufactured goods (foreign demand), and $(X_m - M_m)$ is the net exports of manufactured goods. If the demand (domestic consumption + exports) declines, then output has to decline under the goods market clearing condition. Besides, if demand increases, but imports increase faster, domestic output will fall as well.

- **Has the demand for the manufactured goods declined?**

The demand for manufactured goods consists of domestic and foreign ones (exports). Table 8 shows the change of real final consumption expenditure and some categories of real goods consumption. The final consumption expenditure accounts for around 76% of Canadian GDP in 2018. During the 1981-2000, 2000-2009 and 2009-2018 periods, the durable goods consumption increased by 126.61%, 45.26% and 40.02% respectively and the non-durable goods consumption increased by 26.19%, 16.25% and 15.39% respectively. None of the goods consumption in any category listed had a decline during these periods. Therefore there is no evidence that the domestic demand for the manufactured goods declined.

Consumption Items	Real Consumption (in 2012 dollars)				Change (Per Cent)		
	1981	2000	2009	2018	81-00	00-09	09-18
Final consumption expenditure	657758.00	1013797.00	1316925.00	1607972.00	54.13	29.90	22.10
Durable goods	33700.00	76366.00	110928.00	155325.00	126.61	45.26	40.02
Non-durable goods	166295.00	209841.00	243949.00	281484.00	26.19	16.25	15.39
Food and non-alcoholic beverages	57499.00	78068.00	89882.00	103644.00	35.77	15.13	15.31
Clothing and footwear	19135.00	24972.00	35099.00	49017.00	30.50	40.55	39.65
Furniture and furnishings	5760.00	8609.00	13334.00	17911.00	49.46	54.88	34.33
New trucks, vans and sport utility vehicles	2150.00	13794.00	20579.00	39217.00	541.58	49.19	90.57
Telecommunication equipment	12.00	373.00	683.00	1460.00	3008.33	83.11	113.76
Audio-visual and photographic equipment	827.00	2698.00	6141.00	9694.00	226.24	127.61	57.86
Information processing equipment	24.00	847.00	2616.00	5558.00	3429.17	208.85	112.46
Major durables for outdoor recreation	2773.00	4037.00	5393.00	6347.00	45.58	33.59	17.69
Jewellery, clocks and watches	2140.00	4187.00	4231.00	4674.00	95.65	1.05	10.47

Source: Statistics Canada, CANSIM Table: 36-10-0225-01 and 36-10-0222-01, and authors' calculations.

Table 8. real final consumption and changes of selected items, Canada.

Table 9 shows the change in Canada's exports of merchandise over-time. The manufacturing sector in Canada accounted for more than two-thirds of all export sales in 2016, while the mining, quarrying and oil and gas extraction industry was responsible for only 10.6% (Statistics Canada 2017). Total merchandise

exports did drop (-5.63%) during the 2000-2009 period, but generated a 42.45% gain between 2000 and 2018, during which the top six categories change in export share using 2000 as a baseline were: motor vehicles and parts (-15.30%); forestry products, building and packaging materials (-16.44%); energy products (+181.75%); consumer goods (+60.41%); electronic and electrical equipment and parts (-25.51%); and metal and non-metallic mineral products (+117.22%).

The demand from exports shows heterogeneous results, but the overall merchandise exports experienced a growth of over 40% from 2000 to 2018. Sharpe et al (2014) found that the shift in US import shares from Canada to emerging markets is “in part explained by the reallocation of manufacturing plants from Western countries to emerging markets like China, where labour costs are much lower”. However, by looking at the data, though growing slowly, exports from Canada to the US still increased by around 7% from 2000 to 2009. Additionally, total manufactured goods of all merchandise exports was much less than the total domestic consumption of durable and nondurable goods combined, which grew quite much. Therefore, there is little evidence that the exports were dragging down the manufacturing output creating a decline, not to mention that it is the domestic consumption and exports combined which matter.

Now, as the domestic demand plus the foreign demand did not decline, the decline of the domestic manufacturing output must be from the supply side—the increasing imports, which replace the domestic production. We will discuss this in the following sub-section.

NAPCS	Nominal Export Value				Change (Per Cent)		
	1988Q1	2000Q1	2009Q1	2018Q1	88-00	00-09	00-18
Total of all merchandise	34,403.80	98,606.60	93,054.10	140,464.30	186.62	-5.63	42.45
Farm, fishing and intermediate food products	1,772.70	3,689.20	6,496.70	9,527.50	108.11	76.10	158.25
Energy products	3,469.70	10,441.60	18,993.40	29,419.20	200.94	81.90	181.75
Metal ores and non-metallic minerals	1,611.40	1,695.30	3,149.00	4,569.90	5.21	85.75	169.56
Metal and non-metallic mineral products	3,643.60	7,091.80	8,531.50	15,404.60	94.64	20.30	117.22
Basic and chemical, plastic and rubber	1,511.60	4,536.40	5,965.20	8,372.30	200.11	31.50	84.56
Forestry products, building and packaging materials	5,827.10	13,441.50	7,641.60	11,231.70	130.67	-43.15	-16.44
Industrial machinery, equipment and parts	1,587.30	5,880.90	6,982.20	8,640.90	270.50	18.73	46.93
Electronic and electrical equipment and parts	1,968.20	8,386.20	6,441.20	6,246.90	326.08	-23.19	-25.51
Motor vehicles and parts	9,415.10	24,907.10	8,975.50	21,095.80	164.54	-63.96	-15.30
Aircraft and other transport. equipment and parts	778.2	3,591.10	4,648.90	4,997.80	361.46	29.46	39.17
Consumer goods	2,613.20	9,525.90	11,282.80	15,280.60	264.53	18.44	60.41
Special transactions trade	205.5	5,419.60	3,946.10	5,677.10	2537.27	-27.19	4.75

Source: Statistics Canada, CANSIM Table: 12-10-0122-01, and authors' calculations.

Table 9. Nominal export value, all merchandise and changes, Canada.

- Is the international trade to blame?

Being open to international trade brings gains from goods and service exchanges and the efficiency of production reallocation. Before 1967, Canada's export sector was mostly resource-oriented, while after that, changes in the composition of export growth largely reflected the development of Canada's export-oriented manufacturing sector, supported by legislation such as the Canada-United States Automotive Products Agreement in 1965, the implementation of the Canada-United States Free Trade Agreement in 1989 and the North American Free Trade Agreement in 1994 (Statistics Canada 2018). By the year of 2000, Canada ran a surplus of merchandise trade of around \$25 billion, and ran a trade balance with most of its major trading partners, with over \$100 billion merchandise trade surplus with the US (see Figure 27). In 2000, 86% of Canada's exports were sent to the US, and 67% of its imports came from the US. At the start of the 2000s, manufactured products accounted for almost three-quarters of total exports. In contrast, shipments of energy products—crude oil and crude bitumen, natural gas and refined petroleum products—accounted for 12% of total exports (Statistics Canada 2018).

Figure 27. Canada's merchandise trade balance by country

Figure 28. Employment and Chinese import penetration (Murray 2017)

Then came China's entry to the WTO (World Trade Organization). The US Congress passed PNTR (Permanent Normal Trade Relations) for China in the late 1990s, and it became effective at the end of 2001. It eliminated the possibility of a sudden tariff spike on Chinese imports and thus removed uncertainty for investors (Pierce and Schott 2016). Coincidentally, this is also the start of Canada's decline in real manufacturing output, which makes one wonder if the two are related. From Figure 27, one can easily notice that since 2000, Canada's merchandise trade deficit with China increased to \$32.5 billion by 2008, and \$52.6 billion in 2019 (larger than the US's trade deficit with China in proportion to GDP), and nearly 93% of the total deficit. Figure 28 shows the Chinese import penetration increasing from less than 2% to

9%, while manufacturing employment decreased by over 25%. As of 2017, the merchandise imports from China accounted for nearly 36% of Canada's total manufacturing output. Based on this relationship, imports from Mexico should have played a similar effect, however the deficit with Mexico was much smaller than China, especially before 2008 when the major part of the decline happened.

Traditional trade theories such as the Ricardian model and the specific-factor model predict that under free trade, countries will export products of their comparative advantages. The factor proportion (endowment) theories such as the Heckscher-Ohlin(-Samuelson) model which is also based on comparative advantages predict that a country will export products which more intensively use its relatively more abundant factors/resources. Different countries export goods they specialize in and import what they do not. This is in line with the empirical data. As shown in Figure 11 "real GDP within the manufacturing sector", since 2000, labour intensive manufacturing such as textile and clothing, computer and electronics, electric and appliance, and furniture started their secular decline. Manufacturing in food, beverage and tobacco; petroleum and chemical products; and machinery which are Canada's endowments, slowed down, but still retained their upward trends. From Figure 29, we can see that Canada's imports from China are mostly consumer goods, electronics and electrical equipment and parts, and industry machinery and equipment, whereas Canada's major surplus to China comes from farm, fishing and intermediate food products; metal ores and non-metallic minerals; and forestry products, building and packaging materials.

Capeluck et al (2015) argued that the declining transportation costs have made imported manufactured goods relatively cheaper, leading to both the offshoring of manufacturing production, increasing import competition, and the rise of the global value chains. Imports in one industry will largely affect demand for inputs from upstream industries. Murray (2017) found that the direct effect of rising Chinese import competition in Canadian manufacturing was a net loss of 105,000 manufacturing jobs over the 2001-2011 period, which amounted to 21% of the actual observed decline in manufacturing employment over that period (508,000 jobs). He also noted that manufacturing job loss in Canada was proportionally larger than the US, which was due to Canadian industries having more exposure to Chinese imports than American industries did. He also mentioned that the localities that exhibited the largest increases in Chinese import exposure over the period were all located in Quebec or Ontario, which partly explains why Ontario got hit especially hard as described in Section 2.1.

Figure 29. Canada's merchandise trade with China, the US, and Mexico, 2017

A question may arise - since imports from the US are much larger than China (almost five times in 2008), why is US import competition not the cause of the decline in the Canadian manufacturing sector?

First, Canada and the US had had from very low trade barriers to later free trade agreements for at least the later half of the 20th century, and the two economies have been highly integrated. Canada's imports from the US have not experienced a significant increase during the 2000s. The US imports from Canada, though slowed down the growth after 2000, still grew. In fact, as shown in Figure 27, The US merchandise trade deficit with Canada had widened between 2000 and 2008, previously Canada consistently kept merchandise trade surplus with the US for two decades (which means Canada had net exports to the US). As of 2017 (Figure 29), Canada maintained a rough balance with the US in most industries (farm, fishing and food products; metal, non-metallic and mineral products; chemical, plastic and rubber products; motor vehicles and parts; aircraft and transportation; consumer goods), and had an over 70 billion surplus in energy products.

Secondly, as the two economies are integrated, the manufacturing supply chains of two countries have also been integrated over a long period of time. For example, Canada has many upstream supplies for the auto and aviation industries of the US, and the US provides refinery facilities for the Canadian oil processing. Goods are being shipped between borders every day and many intermediate goods are sent across the border back and forth for next stages of processing. As a result, the value counted in the customs can be double counted (otherwise it's impossible that total manufacturing GDP for Canada is less than 200 billion, but

Canada exports over 350 billion worth of goods to the US). This is also demonstrated by the report from the Conference Board of Canada (Armstrong 2012) which states that the traditional way for accounting in exports and imports at customs has much more double counting than the value-added way. For example, in 1999, Canada imported around \$199 billion from the US, but the number dropped to \$119 billion using the value-added approach, therefore, the true import volumes from the US to Canada should be quite discounted.

Thirdly, the demand based trade theories such as the Linder's hypothesis argues that countries with similar levels or overlaps of demands (such as similar GDP per capita) will trade more and develop similar industries to trade similar but differentiated goods. According to intra-industry trade models such as Krugman (1980) and Melitz (2003), similar industries between similar countries will induce higher output, higher productivity and a larger variety of goods for each country. Autor (2018) stated that for the first three or four decades after World War II, the reason that there was little cause to question the benefits of trade was that most trade occurred between nations with similar average incomes, which meant that any distributional impacts were limited. Trade theory identifies low-wage countries as a likely source of disruption to high-wage labor markets (Krugman 2008). Conversely to the US imports, most of Chinese imports are final products that don't need Canada's upstream firms to provide inputs (see Figure 29, including consumer goods, electronic and electrical equipment, and machinery), thus tend to destroy the demands for not only the domestic brands, but also the upstream suppliers.

Additionally, all the trade models mentioned above assume free trade, so that goods are freely moving across borders and the "gain from trade" largely comes from export sectors (such as increase in productivity and real national income). Otherwise, there is still a gain from more variety of consumer goods and lower prices of production inputs, but tradable sector workers have no gains or loss, and the country has to borrow to finance its net imports (trade deficit), which we will discuss in Section 4. Therefore, if a country's trading partner sets trade barriers, then the expected gains of this country from trade will not be achieved. For example, if Canada or the US face obstacles to export their technological products, while they can freely import low-value added goods from other countries, then neither skilled workers nor unskilled workers in Canada or the US will be better off as predicted by trade theories. Trade with China has not been real free trade, as China reportedly sets many tariff and non-tariff trade barriers for its trading partners. In fact, many countries have unfair trade practices, however, China's are particularly severe and its export volumes are especially large, so its impacts are enormous. According to Scott (2017), China's unfair trade practices include: illegal export subsidies and dumping, non-tariff barriers that block imports and foreign competition, labour rights repression, lax environment protection, currency manipulation, forced technology transfer and intellectual property theft. A brief from the CSIS (Center for Strategic and

International Studies 2020) describes how the Chinese government subsidizes the maritime industry and makes Chinese companies increasingly dominant across its supply chains. These subsidies include \$127 billion directed financing from the Chinese state banks. According to the report of USTR's (US Trade Representative 2018), China also partakes in cyber espionage of technological and commercial secrets, discriminatory licencing restrictions, and poor IP protection for foreign companies. All of these behaviors not only give Chinese products unfair price advantages which have eliminated many foreign firms that could have otherwise survived and competed in both domestic and international markets; but also make it harder for foreign products to enter the Chinese market, and foreign companies to operate within China, while the Chinese exports can almost freely access the world market including Canada's.

The US has more abundant research on the effects of the Chinese import competition. Autor, Dorn, and Hanson (2013) estimated import competition contributed to a 25% decline of aggregate US manufacturing employment after 2000. Autor, Dorn, and Hanson (2015) further found that regions exposed to imports from China experienced a significant slump in employment, especially in manufacturing industries, including high-skilled jobs. Acemoglu et al (2014) found that imports from China surging from 10.9% in 2001 to 23.1% in total imports in 2011, was a major force behind both recent reductions in US manufacturing employment, and through input-output linkages and other general equilibrium channels, weakened overall US job growth. The estimated job loss from rising Chinese import competition over 1999-2011 was 2.0-2.4 million, with exposed upstreams sectors facing import competition having large negative impacts. Holmes (2011) did a case study on the home furniture industry and highlighted that the making of high-quality wood furniture, which requires labor intensive craftsmanship, is hit hard, with a majority of the large plants shutting down and employment dropping by half. The growth of the US trade deficit with China was responsible for the displacement of 2.6 million manufacturing jobs in this period, or about 75.4% of manufacturing jobs lost (BLS 2016). Empirical research by Autor, Dorn, and Hanson (2012) has shown that "increased exposure to low-income country imports is associated with rising unemployment, decreased labor-force participation, and increased use of disability and other transfer benefits, as well as with lower wages." From an export-import job transition perspective, trade creates new jobs in exporting industries and destroys jobs when imports replace the output of domestic firms. Because trade deficits have risen over the past decade, more jobs have been displaced by imports than created by exports (Bivens 2008). Exposure to imports can accelerate the adoption of automated processes which further reduce jobs (Bloom, Draca and Van Reenen 2016, Pierce and Schott 2016). Pierce and Schott (2016) pointed out three channels by which granting China PNTR may have affected manufacturing employment: 1) it increased the incentive for US firms to incur sunk costs of shifting operations to China or of partnering with a Chinese manufacturer, 2) it provided Chinese producers with incentives to enter or further invest in exporting to the US market, and 3)

it provided an incentive for US firms to invest in labor-saving technology or to shift the mix of products they produced to less labor-intensive ones. Studies have also found sizable adverse effects of Chinese imports on US firm sales, investment, patents, and research and development (Autor et al. 2017, Pierce and Schott 2017).

- **Outsourcing overseas**

Outsourcing refers to the acquisition by firms of intermediate inputs or final products (either goods or services) from external suppliers. Firms may decide to outsource in order to reduce their costs or to focus on their core activities or avoid difficulties due to regulatory and technological developments (Murray 2015). Besides cheaper costs, as mentioned above, unfair trade practices of some trading partners such as China, include higher trade or non-trade barriers, forcing multinationals to ship production overseas to circumvent the cost of barriers.

In Canada, Calver (2016) points out that professional and business services (PBS) sectors outsourcing has also made a contribution to the decline of Canada's manufacturing sector, though not a major driver. Capeluck (2015) notes that rising labour productivity and falling demand were the major culprits, and the true impact of manufacturing outsourcing likely lies somewhere between. Capeluck found that manufacturing outsourcing accounted for 21.1% of the decline in manufacturing's employment share, while PBS and FS (financial services) outsourcing only accounted for 3.1% between 1976 and 2008.

In the US, Setser (2017) found that the US producers also may close plants and shift production overseas or simply expand production in other countries to take advantage of lower wages, higher subsidies, or lower tax rates. Using establishment-level data on multinational firms from the Census Bureau, Boehm, Flaaen, and Pandalai-Nayar (2015) estimate that the offshoring of intermediate inputs, which they find is primarily done by multinational companies, substitutes for US employment. Their structural model estimates indicate that offshoring of intermediate inputs by multinational companies accounts for 13 percent of the decline in US manufacturing employment between 1993 and 2011. Berlingieri (2014) found that changes in the composition of intermediate inputs for all industries accounted for 25.3% of the fall in manufacturing's share of total employment and PBS outsourcing accounted for 16.1% in the United States over the 1948-2002 period.

- **Exchange rate**

Canada's relatively superior performance of the manufacturing sector in the 1980s (1983-1989) and 1990s (1994-2003) as shown in Figure 31, compared to other OECD countries, stemmed primarily from a differential trend in relative manufacturing prices from exchange-rate cycles (Statistics Canada 2019). A weaker dollar is not necessarily a positive thing especially in the long run, but in the short run, it can give the export sector a boost, as their products are cheaper in the global market. A weaker dollar also makes imports more expensive and reduces import displacement of Canadian production. Around three fourths of Canadian exports are sent to the US, so the exchange rate of USD/CAD affects the imports and exports between US and Canada through pricing. Canadian manufacturing employment expanded in Canada from 1994 to 2003 and was in sync with USD/CAD exchange rate depreciation during this period (Figure 30). Then after 2004, the decline was partly attributable to Canadian dollar appreciation. However in 2009 or after 2011, the manufacturing employment did not rebound, even as Canadian dollar rebounded (the same applies to the output). This suggests the sudden collapse after 2004 had other factors at play.

Figure 30. USD/CAD exchange rate, 1989-2019.

Figure 31. Canada vs US in manufacturing employment.

- Slowdown of labour productivity after 2000

As described in Section 3.1, the labour productivity growth in the manufacturing sector is hardly to blame for the employment losses, however, its slowdown could have contributed to the decline of the real manufacturing output (that is, if the amount of labour keeps constant, lower labour productivity growth results in lower real output growth). Labour productivity in the long run is determined by human capital, physical capital and technological progress. Any under-investments of these three factors can undermine the labour productivity growth. Figure 32 shows that labour productivity in the manufacturing sector has diverged from the US since the 1980s.

Figure 32. Relative labour productivity in Canada vs. the United States (Bank of Canada)

- **Industry-specific factors**

As shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15, “nominal and real GDP within the manufacturing sector”, some sub-sectors whose real GDP have declined after 2000 such as transportation, metal and mineral products, wood and paper products and petroleum and chemical products were less likely to be affected by import competition (for example, from China or Mexico). By looking at Table 9 “nominal export value, all merchandise and change”, exports of these sub-sectors between 2000 and 2009 either declined or had significantly slowed growth. Therefore, they are more likely to be caused by weaker external demand or a decline in the competitiveness of Canadian products on the international market. However, Statistics Canada’s report (2017) asserted that even if the contribution of the Canadian transportation equipment industry on the growth of the durable goods sector had been the same as in the US, growth in the Canadian durable goods sector would still have been much weaker than in the US. Therefore some industry-specific factors cannot fully explain the decline.

4. Does the Decline Matter?

The decline of Canadian manufacturing sector especially in the 2000s, and the possible causes beg the question: does this matter? To answer the question, this section examines aspects of the health of the economy, labour market, international trade, global competitiveness and social impacts.

4.1 Health of economy

To determine the health of the macroeconomy of a country, the following indicators are usually measured: economic growth rate, employment rate, and price stability. For example, one can use productivity growth to measure growth, or CPI/PPI to measure price stability. In this subsection, we examine whether the decline of the manufacturing sector impacts the macroeconomy.

- Manufacturing and productivity growth

In the long run, the GDP growth is driven by growth in productivity and the labour force (hours worked). Labour productivity growth is not exogenous but rather is affected by a multitude of factors including intensity and quality of capital and labour growth. Multifactor productivity growth is driven by many factors, including but not limited to innovation, economies of scale and scope, technological progress (Capeluck 2015). Poloz (2016) points to the importance of productivity growth: “improved productivity is essential to compete internationally, which is itself essential to maintaining or growing a business.”

Figure 33. Multifactor productivity growth by business sector industry, Canada, 1997-2014. (from Calver 2016)

Historically, the manufacturing sector had a relatively high growth rate in both labour and multi-factor productivities. The labour productivity growth in the manufacturing sector quite outpaced the average business sector and most other sectors. Table 2 shows historical data of labour productivity growth by sector in Canada from 1961 to 2011. Evidently, the compound annual labour productivity growth rate of the manufacturing sector was 2.81%. Although this number is lower than information and cultural industries; crop and animal production; forestry and logging, and wholesale trade, it is higher than the average business sector (1.99%), including transportation and warehousing (2.44%), finance (1.1%); professional, scientific and technical services (0.79%); and healthcare and social assistance (-0.03%). As shown in Figure 33, with

regard to the multifactor productivity growth rate, the manufacturing sector was higher than most other sectors between 1997 and 2014. Thus, if other sectors that have higher or similar growth rates in labour or multi-factor productivity do not fill the gap, overall labour and multifactor productivity growth will necessarily slow down. Unfortunately, past data shows that emerging sectors such as finance, professional services had lower growth rates in both labour and multi-factor productivities in the 2000s, precluding such sectors as replacements for the manufacturing sector.

Apart from the productivity growth rate, the manufacturing sector also tends to have a higher level of productivity. Take, for example, labour productivity; the manufacturing sector generates more GDP per hour worked than many other sectors. As shown in Figure 36, GDP per hour worked generated by manufacturing jobs is \$66, lower than mining (\$166), oil and gas (\$460), utilities (\$196), information and cultural studies (\$90), and finance and real-estate (\$88), but higher than construction (\$47), wholesale (\$65), transportation and warehousing (\$48), healthcare and social work (\$45), professional, science and technology (\$50), etc. More notably, in terms of total hours worked, sectors that generate lower average GDP per hour worked than the manufacturing sector account for 72.7% of total hours worked in 2016. Sectors that generate higher GDP per hour worked only account for 15.1% of total hours worked.

The manufacturing sector tends to have higher rates of productivity growth because of its high levels of R&D spending, and capital intensity (Scott 2017). The research of the Federal Reserve of St. Louis (Santacreu and Zhu 2018) found that the manufacturing sector has a higher share in total R&D spending. This can explain why the manufacturing sector contributes more to productivity growth, despite its much lower share in GDP. The same study studied 24 countries in the OECD during 2000-2014, and found that on average the manufacturing sector contributed to 92.01% of exports, 64.86% of R&D spending, and 42.32% of productivity growth. In comparison, the service sector contributed 1.09%, 33.90% and 24.77%, respectively. Moreover, higher R&D spending can explain why the manufacturing sector also has relatively higher levels of productivity (as shown in Figure 36). More importantly, many countries (e.g. Germany, Japan, the United States and China) have been rapidly shifting to advanced manufacturing, such as autonomous robots, integrated computational materials engineering, digital manufacturing, industrial internet and flexible automation, and additive manufacturing (BCG 2015). This BCG report also claims that advanced-manufacturing technologies can boost productivity by dramatically increasing flexibility; such technology offers customers the option to customize based on their requirements. Manufacturers can also make products in small batches for specific customers, adjust production lines in response to design changes, and speed time to market by generating prototypes quickly.

Contribution of Each Sector (percent)					
Sector	Share employment	Share value added	Share exports	Share R&D spending	Productivity growth
Agriculture	2.34	4.61	6.90	1.24	32.91
Manufacturing	16.92	16.96	92.01	64.86	42.32
Service	80.74	78.43	1.09	33.90	24.77

SOURCE: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development database and authors' calculations.

Table 10. Contribution of each sector, OECD countries, 2000-2014. (Santacreu and Zhu 2018)

The decline of the output share, the slowdown in manufacturing productivity, and the relatively high level of productivity of the manufacturing sector contributed to the slowdown of the overall productivity growth in Canada. Take, for example, labour productivity. The labour productivity growth rate of the manufacturing sector has outperformed the business sector in the past (see Figure 12), and the manufacturing labour productivity level has been higher than many other sectors as described above. Thus, if the manufacturing share in real GDP shrinks and manufacturing productivity growth slows down, by mathematics, the overall labour productivity must slow down as a result. As shown in Table 11, the annual compound manufacturing labour productivity growth rate during 2000-2007 was significantly lower than the 1990s. The overall labour productivity growth rate during the 2000s was also lower than before (Figure 12). Manufacturing sub-sectors that had negative or close to zero annual labour productivity growth between 2000 and 2007 account for almost 60% of the total manufacturing real output. Sectors of negative productivity growth include manufacturing of beverage and tobacco, petroleum and chemical, computer and electronic, electrical, and furniture products. Interestingly, many sub-sectors which endured negative labour productivity growth also had dramatic real output decline, such as textile and clothing, computer and electronic, electric, and furniture products. This may be due to the fact that when these sectors face import competition or offshoring (as discussed in Section 3), investments in R&D - which could boost productivity growth - also plummeted. In fact, several studies have found sizable adverse effects of Chinese imports on US firm sales, investment, patents, and research and development (Autor et al. 2017, Pierce and Schott 2017). All in all, the slowdown in the manufacturing labour productivity growth contributed to the overall labour productivity slowdown. Had the manufacturing kept the output growth rate or labour productivity growth rate as prior to 2000, the overall labour productivity growth rate would have been higher. Consequently, as the overall productivity in Canada slowed down, the GDP growth in the 2000s also slowed down (Figure 34).

NAICS Codes	Labour Productivity Growth Annual Compound (Per Cent)		Share in Real Manufacturing GDP (Per Cent)		Real GDP Change (Per Cent)
	87-00	00-07	2000	2007	00-07
Manufacturing	6.63	0.75	100	100	-4.81
Food manufacturing	4.19	0.18	9.00	10.81	13.81
Beverage and tobacco product manufacturing	6.24	-5.82	3.79	3.42	-14.62
Textile and textile product mills	3.31	-0.85	1.47	0.90	-42.11
Clothing, Leather and allied product manufacturing	5.15	-0.45	2.03	1.02	-52.10
Wood product manufacturing	4.55	6.44	3.77	4.38	10.22
Paper manufacturing	6.09	3.06	5.08	4.89	-8.91
Printing and related support activities	0.40	0.49	2.99	3.16	0.29
Petroleum and coal products manufacturing	6.51	-9.69	5.37	6.20	9.35
Chemical manufacturing	8.44	-0.79	9.30	9.62	-2.04
Plastics and rubber products manufacturing	6.04	0.77	4.51	4.89	2.76
Non-metallic mineral product manufacturing	4.37	0.81	2.66	3.49	24.48
Primary metal manufacturing	8.66	1.57	5.54	6.31	7.77
Fabricated metal product manufacturing	3.58	-0.29	7.47	7.82	-0.76
Machinery manufacturing	5.29	0.13	6.70	7.28	2.92
Computer and electronic product manufacturing	18.74	-1.94	6.79	4.15	-42.20
Electrical equipment, appliance and component manufacturing	7.39	-1.18	2.62	1.97	-28.93
Transportation equipment manufacturing	10.52	1.16	14.29	14.25	-5.53
Furniture and related product manufacturing	7.14	-1.95	3.34	2.85	-19.02

Source: Statistics Canada, CANSIM Table 36-10-0217-01, and authors' calculations.

Table 11. Labour productivity growth and real GDP share of manufacturing sub-sectors, Canada.

Figure 34. GDP growth rate by year, Canada.

- Manufacturing and its backward- and forward-linkages in the economy

The manufacturing sector plays a much bigger role than statistics show regarding share of GDP. Houseman (2018) found that through supply chain linkages, the manufacturing sector has an outsized effect on the economy. Approximately half of the labour needed in the production of manufactured goods in the United States and other advanced countries is employed outside the manufacturing sector. This does not consider

that increased employed manufacturing workers spend more in the economy, and create new jobs. A report from the MAPI Foundation and Inforum at University of Maryland in 2016 found that the conventional measurement of the manufacturing's share of the US GDP is grossly underestimated; one dollar of domestic manufacturing value-added destined for manufactured goods final demand generates another \$3.60 of value-added elsewhere. This is because manufacturing output consists only of manufacturing establishments (i.e., plants), irrespective of the other industries owned by the firm. Other industries include R&D, management, wholesale, centralized logistics and accounting. The manufacturing related output also has upstream supplies and downstream sales. The total value chain of manufactured goods for final demand supports 38,854,000 full-time jobs and \$2.5 trillion, or 30,095,000 non-manufacturing jobs and 8,760,000 full-time manufacturing jobs in the value chain of manufactured goods final demand. In this way, the domestic manufactured goods value chain actually accounts for 29% of GDP and manufacturing value-added committed to nonmanufacturing value chains adds another 3% of GDP, totaling up to 32% of GDP. Another research estimates that the manufacturing sector generated \$6.2 trillion in gross output (net sales) in 2014, more than one-third (35.6%) of US GDP in that year, and 40.5% of private-sector economic output (BEA 2016). In 2014, manufacturing supported approximately 17.4 million indirect jobs, in addition to the 12.2 million people directly employed, for a total of 29.6 million jobs directly and indirectly supported, more than one-fifth (21.3%) of total US employment in 2014 (Scott 2015, BLS 2016).

Bivens (2019) had a similar but slightly different finding that production in a given economic sector involves linkages with other sectors - that is, suppliers in other industries (backward linkages), and wages earned in the production and supplier sectors that are spent elsewhere (forward linkages). He studied two ways to measure how intensive an industry's backward and forward linkages are. The first way estimates the ripple effects of a given number of jobs lost in an industry. Every 100 jobs in the durable manufacturing sector indirectly creates 744 jobs (backward and forward linkages). Only utilities (957) and real estate (880) sectors are higher. The second way takes one given dollar value of final demand for an industry's output and calculates how much of this final demand spills over into backward- and forward-linked industries. The result shows that durable manufacturing is 16.5, and non-durable manufacturing is 14.7, with only the real estate (22.6) and art/entertainment/recreation (22.5) being higher. Bivens claims that is why policymakers decided not to let auto firms fail and become casualties of the financial crisis of late 2008.

- **Manufacturing and fiscal impacts**

A sudden decline of the local manufacturing sector may lead to local fiscal impacts. Research found that trade shocks mostly fell onto the local manufacturing sector and its spillover in surrounding non-manufacturing sectors, and other local sectors did not usually fill the gap. As a result, local fiscal revenue

and public services became constrained. Feler and Senses (2016) analyzed the impact of trade-induced income shocks on the size of local government, and the provision of public services. They found that for areas in the US, which had the loss of local manufacturing jobs due to increasing import competition from China, declining labour demand and incomes were correlated with declines in housing prices and business activity. These translates into less revenue, which constrains the ability of local governments to provide public services. Meanwhile, state and federal governments usually have limited ability to smooth local shocks. The outcome is greater inequality not only in income but also in the quality of public services and amenities across US jurisdictions. Since high-skilled workers and new growth industries tend to value high quality public goods, areas negatively affected by trade shocks face greater difficulty in providing these goods, which, in turn, makes it more challenging for them to compete economically against other localities and recover from shocks (Black 1999, Moretti 2012).

- **Manufacturing and the depressed inflation**

Apart from low GDP and productivity growth, both Canada and the United States entered a “secular” low inflation age during the past decade. In theory, as the domestic manufacturing sector declined, exposure to cheaper foreign imports that replaced the share of domestic manufactured goods contributed to the lower inflation. Bai and Stumpner (2019) estimated the size of US consumer gains from Chinese imports during 2004-2015, and using barcode-level price and expenditure data, they constructed inflation rates. Using Chinese exports to Europe as an instrument, they found significant negative effects of Chinese imports on US prices by a 0.19 ppt annual reduction in the price index for consumer traded goods. This effect is driven by both changes in the prices of existing goods and the entry of new goods. This effect is similar across consumer groups by income or region. Abdih et al (2016) found that foreign factors (rather than domestic) drive core goods inflation, with a specific channel operating through import prices. In turn, the latter was found to be primarily determined by the strength of the dollar as well as inflation in countries that are major non-oil commodity exporters to the U.S.—most notably, China, Canada, the Euro area, and Mexico. The evidence from Francis (2007) suggests that, following its accession to the WTO, China played a significant role in restructuring global trade and hence affected relative prices. In the market for clothing, the phase-out of quotas seems to have significantly increased the availability of inexpensive clothing from China. As a result, the global clothing prices have fallen, and expenditure on imported Chinese clothing has risen.

4.2 Labour Market

How is the decline of the manufacturing sector an issue for the labour market? Capeluck (2015) argues that generally speaking, whether the decline in manufacturing's employment share is an issue depends primarily on the quality of the new jobs. If the quality of new jobs is worse than the quality of those lost, then the decline in manufacturing's employment share should be considered an issue. Calver (2016) also notes that the loss of high-paying domestic jobs not offset by gains from trade should be an area of concern. Meanwhile, a short period of shock caused by the decline of the manufacturing sector can disrupt the labour market, and cause multiple distributional impacts, such as those for the displaced workers. Moreover, long-term impacts of a secular low level of manufacturing employment will also be an issue.

- **Impact of manufacturing sector decline on labour market**

The decline of the manufacturing sector due to import competition or offshoring led to a noticeable loss of jobs, and may not have been offset by other sectors in Canada. As analyzed in Section 3, import competition or offshoring (especially the influx of Chinese imports) played a significant role in the decline of the manufacturing sector. Murray et al (2017) used an instrumental variable strategy to estimate that total job losses in Canada from rising Chinese import competition. They estimate that a total of 150,000 to 170,000 jobs were lost over the 2001-2011 period, of which the manufacturing sector accounts for at least 105,000 (21% of the total decline 508,000 in manufacturing employment). However, they claim that the employment effects of indirect exposure to import competition via input-output linkages is small in Canada. Notably, they also find that rising Chinese import competition reduced employment in all exposed sectors by 255,400 jobs, which accounts for 74.2% of the total observed employment decline - that is, 344,300 jobs lost in exposed sectors over the 2001-2011 period. Total employment loss was partially offset by an employment increase of 152,400 in the non-exposed non-tradable sectors, most of which are service sectors. Ultimately, however, the employment gains they measured in the non-traded non-exposed sector were insufficient to offset the losses in the exposed sectors.

Loss of manufacturing jobs contributed to wage inequality in Canada. Breau and Rigby (2009) investigated the impact of trade shocks on the local manufacturing sector in terms of wages and wage inequality across industries and regions in Canada. Results from wage regression models show that import competition from low-income countries has a significant impact on wage inequality in Canada by lowering the wages of less-educated workers but sparing those of highly educated workers. The negative effect of import competition on the wages of less-skilled workers is more pronounced in Quebec and in the Prairie provinces, as well as in labor-intensive and product-differentiated industries.

Compared to Canada, the US has more research on this. Autor, Dorn, and Hanson (2012) estimate that rising exposure to low-cost Chinese imports lowers labor force participation and reduces wages in local

labor markets. In particular, they find that increased import competition has a statistically significant depressing effect on non-manufacturing wages. “For the oldest group (50–64), 84% of the decline in manufacturing employment is accounted for by the rise in nonparticipation, relative to 71% among the prime-age group and 68% among the younger group”. Thus, they conclude that more than two-thirds of all workers displaced by growing competition with Chinese imports dropped out of the labor force.

Autor, Dorn, and Hanson (2013) found that rising imports cause higher unemployment and reduced wages in local labor markets. Import competition explains 25% of the decline in US manufacturing employment. Transfer payments for unemployment, disability, retirement, and healthcare also rise sharply in more trade-exposed labor markets. Autor, Dorn, and Hanson (2014) also found that for regions affected by Chinese imports, the estimated dollar increase in per capita SSDI (Social Security Disability Insurance) payments is more than 30 times as large as the estimated dollar increases in TAA (Trade Adjustment Assistance) payments. Autor, Dorn, and Hanson (2016) later found that adjustment in local labor markets is remarkably slow, with depressed wages and labor-force participation rates and elevated unemployment rates for at least a full decade after the China trade shock commenced. Exposed workers experienced greater job churning and reduced lifetime income.

At the national level, employment fell in US industries more exposed to import competition. This is unsurprising. However, offsetting employment gains in other industries have yet to materialize. Multiple research studies (Acemoglu et al. 2016, Charles, Hurst, and Notowidigdo 2016) found that the sudden and large losses of manufacturing jobs in the 2000s was to a large degree responsible for the weak job growth and poor labor market outcomes among less-educated workers during that decade. Of note, the housing boom in the early 2000s initially masked some of the effects of manufacturing job losses. Also, Acemoglu et al (2016) did not find statistically significant evidence of employment gains in non-exposed industries to offset declines in the exposed sector. They attributed limited employment gains in non-exposed industries to strong aggregate demand effects operating within the local labour market. Scott (2013) estimated the gains and losses associated with direct changes in employment was caused by growing U.S.-China trade deficits between 2001 and 2011. The key finding in that study is that jobs displaced by imports from China actually paid 17.0% more than jobs exporting to China: \$1,021.66 per week in import-competing industries versus \$872.89 per week in exporting industries. Scott (2013) argued that standard trade theory assumes that economic integration leads to “gains from trade”, as workers move from low-productivity jobs in import-competing industries into higher-productivity jobs in export-competing industries. However, this assumption is proven incorrect: on average, import-competing jobs pay better than alternative jobs in export-producing industries. Therefore, simple trade expansion which increases total trade, with no underlying change in the trade balance, will result in a net loss to workers as they move from higher-paying

jobs in import-competing industries to lower-paying jobs in exporting industries. Between 2001 and 2011 (Scott 2013), growing exports to China supported 538,000 US jobs, but growing imports displaced 3,280,200 jobs, for a net loss of 2.7 million US jobs. Thus, net 2.7 million workers were displaced from jobs making \$1,021.66 per week on average, and (if they were lucky enough to find jobs) were mostly pushed into jobs in non-tradable industries paying an average of only \$791.14 per week (a decline of 22.6%). In total, US workers suffered a direct net wage loss of \$37 billion per year due to trade with China.

Can jobs in service sectors replace the manufacturing sector?

Hirshhorn (2013) argues that service sector jobs in Canada tend to “have a higher incidence of part-time and temporary workers, rely more on unpaid overtime and make greater use of flexible work arrangements” while jobs created in innovative industries that require high-skill workers, are likely to improve the living standards of Canadians. Murray (2017) estimated that the employment gains they measure in the non-traded non-exposed sector in Canada were not sufficient to offset the losses in the trade exposed sectors. Meanwhile, manufacturing provides good jobs with better wages and benefits for workers without a college degree, who make up nearly two-thirds of the US labor force (Scott 2016). Manufacturing jobs tend to be of less income inequality. An IMF report (2019) that studied the level of labor income inequality within industry (70% of which is accounted for by manufacturing) found that the inequality within industry is indeed somewhat lower than within services in a sample of 20 advanced economies.

Source: Statistics Canada, RBC Economics Research

Figure 35. Median hourly wage by ind., Canada (from RBC)

Source: Statistics Canada, RBC Economics Research

Figure 36. Per hour GDP/labour compensation by ind. Canada (from RBC)

Section 4.2 describes how manufacturing jobs generate higher GDP per hour worked than many other sectors, namely, a higher level of productivity. Manufacturing jobs also pay higher wages than many services jobs. According to Statistics Canada (2019), Canada’s total labour force is 18,657 thousand, with 14,729 thousand in service sectors. Of all sectors, those with hourly pay lower than or equal to manufacturing (around \$23/hour in 2017, see Figure 35) are: agriculture (277 thousand), wholesale (646 thousand), retail (2,138 thousand), transport/warehousing (991 thousand), administration support/waste

management (777 thousand), information/culture/recreation (787 thousand), accommodation/food service (1,235 thousand) and other private industries (803 thousand). That being said, about 41% of total jobs or 52% of services jobs pay less than manufacturing jobs. If those jobs which are just slightly higher (within \$5) than manufacturing in hourly pay are accounted for—that is: construction (1,438 thousand), finance (1,174 thousand), healthcare (2,407 thousand)—then about 68% of total jobs or 86% of services jobs pay less or within \$5 hourly pay difference than manufacturing jobs. In other words, less than 23% of total employment or 14% of service jobs pay more than \$5 an hour than manufacturing jobs. And these high-paying jobs are limited in quantity and are hard to get for many Canadians including the displaced manufacturing workers.

In the US, as of September 2015, average hourly compensation in manufacturing was around \$8 higher (27.2 percent higher) than industries that have gained jobs since the beginning of the 2009 recession and were mostly service industries (Scott 2016). After 2000, around 5 million manufacturing jobs were lost in the US. This does not include counterfactual, meaning manufacturing employment growth that may have followed proportional increase of the total employment growth. 5 million is around 4% of 2018's US total employment and could be higher if counting the job loss in upstream/downstream manufacturing and non-manufacturing firms. Spence (2011) states that as displaced workers in lower levels of tradable sectors (e.g., manufacturing) were forced to move to lower levels of the non-tradable sector (e.g. service sectors), wages could be suppressed because the non-tradable sector is likely to generate fewer jobs than is expected in the future. This is a typical distributional impact of globalization in the past.

- **Manufacturing sector create more jobs beyond itself**

Manufacturing jobs lead to the creation of more jobs in other sectors. Houseman (2018) claims that, with just under 10% of US employment, the manufacturing sector has an outsized effect on the economy through supply chain linkages. Approximately half of the labor needed in the production of manufactured goods in the United States and other advanced countries is employed outside the manufacturing sector. Moretti (2010) estimates that each additional manufacturing job in a city generates 1.6 non-manufacturing jobs. Multiplier effects are higher for skilled jobs: an additional skilled manufacturing job in a city generates an estimated 2.5 jobs in local goods-producing and service sectors. Manufacturing firms tend to hire more employees than sectors such as finance. For example, an estimate by the New York Times showed that the entire Wall Street firms in 2008 hired about 200,000 employees, whereas the transportation equipment manufacturer Bombardier employed 69,500 workers including R&D in 2017.

Additionally, the advent of advanced manufacturing brings the promising prospect of creating more high-paying jobs. As mentioned in Section 4.1, advanced manufacturing includes autonomous robots, integrated

computational materials engineering, digital manufacturing, industrial internet and flexible automation, and additive manufacturing, which will not only improve productivity and output, but also generate the demand for high-skilled jobs. However, without a healthy manufacturing sector, advanced manufacturing will build on nothing.

4.3 International Trade

In Section 3, we have described how international trade, specifically import competition and offshoring played a significant role in the decline of Canadian manufacturing sector during the 2000s. As an open economy, international trade plays a vital role in Canada's economy. For example, total Canadian merchandise trade (exports+imports) posted a record high of nearly \$1.18 trillion in 2018 (Statistics Canada). Therefore, whether and how the decline of the manufacturing sector impacts Canada's international trade is also worth examination.

- Manufacturing sector and international trade

Canada has had a consistent trade deficit in goods and service combined for the past decade. For example, Canada had an overall trade deficit in goods and services of \$43.3 billion in 2018 (Statistics Canada). Poloz (2016) pointed out that a significant shock to Canada's economy has been a steady loss of export capacity (absolute volume of exports) in the years prior to and in the wake of the global financial crisis. Canada's export recovery since 2009 has been impressive but remains incomplete, as at least \$30 billion worth of export capacity was lost in the process and competitiveness challenges continue (Figure 37). As a result, Canada's consistent trade deficit may be partly due to the steady loss of export capacity.

Now, we need to answer two questions: 1. Does consistent weak export capacity or trade deficit matter? 2. Does the decline of the manufacturing sector have an impact on export capacity or trade balance?

Figure 37. Real exports, Canada, the US and the world, 2000-2018.

Question 1: Why is weaker export capacity a problem, and the same question applies to the resulting trade deficit, if imports keep growing?

First, GDP consists of four parts: consumption, government expenditure, investment and net exports ($GDP = C + G + I + NX$). Note that these four components are not exogenous to each other, and if imports are more of capital goods such as industry equipment which can improve production levels, then it may not be harmful. But if consistent negative net exports are due to insufficient export capacity to balance imports, especially when imports are not prominent in capital goods used for production, then its national income, namely the GDP level may be hampered.

Second, a trade deficit means that a country must borrow from abroad to finance this excess of consumption over domestic production (Scott 2018), according to the rule of national income accounting ($Savings = Investments + Net Exports$). This borrowing leads to growing foreign debt that must be paid, with interest (Bivens 2008). As of March of 2016, Canada’s external debt was \$1.6 trillion (IndexMundi). On the other side, trade surplus earned by trading partners will eventually flow back to Canada in the form of foreign capital flows and end up purchasing domestic properties such as Canadian bonds or Canadian assets. As of 2016, the foreign-controlled assets in Canada reached almost \$2 trillion (Statistics Canada). As explained by former Federal Reserve chairman Ben Bernanke (2005), “this can destabilize the domestic economy, as they did in the housing bubble of 2001 to 2007 (or Toronto and Vancouver housing market in Canada’s case)—foreign capital inflows largely piped in property markets rather than production areas.” In these cases, the structure of the domestic economy has become “imbalanced,” in the sense that the housing sector has become too large to be sustainable in a long-run equilibrium, and the manufacturing sector is too small to maintain the number of good, family-sustaining jobs needed to support working-class families (Bernanke 2005). As the consistent trade deficit continues, this means more and more domestic assets will be held by

foreigners. This may raise national security concerns in the future, especially if foreign assets holders are from adversarial countries.

Third, consistent trade deficits mean that “gains from trade” may not be realized. Trade theories suggest that gains from trade include consumer welfare gains such as a wider variety of consumer goods and cheaper imports, and producer welfare gains such as increases in efficiency and productivity, pro-competitive gains, and economy of scale (larger market). In most cases, consumer welfare is achieved by imports and producer welfare by exports. Whether consumer or producer welfare is more important depends on a society’s valuation judgement. However, from the economics perspective, if weight is given too much to consumers rather than producers, the productivity or national production/income may be impaired. In other words, gains from trade not only are measured by consumer welfare such as cheaper goods, variety of goods, but also by producer welfare such as increased efficiency and productivity, pro-competitive gains, and economy of scale. As Canada has been running a consistent trade deficit for the past decade and its manufacturing sector keeps declining, Canadian economy has not achieved what it should have, nor has producer welfare made from “gains from trade”. This fact can not be neglected. Export firms largely contribute to the economy. Baldwin (2016) finds that the 28% of Canadian manufacturing firms were also GVC (global value chain) participants during the 2002-2006 period and were generally larger, more productive and paid higher wages, and these performances continued into future years. As shown in Figure 38, Canadian manufacturing firms who are exporters have more employment, more sales and higher labour productivity for most of the past four decades (Baldwin 2016). All of this means that if unfair trade practices such as unilateral protectionism or mercantilism continue, the undue loss of the manufacturing sector are harmful.

Canadian Manufacturing Firms: Exporters’ Shares

	Fraction of Firms Which are Exporters	Employment Share of Exporters	Sales Share of Exporters
1980s	25%	60%	70%
1990s	35%	70%	80%
2000s	40%	70%	80%

Source: Baldwin and Yan (2016)

Canadian Manufacturing Firms:

Labour Productivity of Exporters Relative to Non-Exporters

	Labour Productivity Ratio
1979-1984	100%
1984-1990	144%
1990-1996	163%
1996-2000	132%
2000-2005	110%
2005-2010	86%

Source: Baldwin and Yan (2016)

Figure 38. Canadian Manufacturing Firms: employment, sales and productivity.

Question 2: Does the decline of the manufacturing sector have an impact on export capacity?

As mentioned in Section 4.1, according to the study (Santacreu and Zhu 2018) on 24 OECD countries, manufacturing output contributes to more than 90% of the exports. Therefore, if a country's manufacturing output level is low, it is more likely to run into trade imbalance. In Figure 39, we have gathered manufacturing and trade data of countries which have GDP per capita over 10,000 USD and are not resource-oriented countries such as Qatar or UAE. From the correlation of manufacturing output as a share of GDP and trade balance as a share of GDP, we can clearly see that countries with higher manufacturing output levels also tend to run trade surplus (the red fitted line).

Figure 39. Correlation of Manufacturing Output and Trade Balance, by country, 2018.

In fact, a report from UNIDO (2018) shows that the nominal share of consumption of manufactured goods in all consumption for most developed countries falls into the narrow range of 36%-42%. For example, the US is around 36% and Canada is 39%. The final consumption expenditure share of GDP for most developed countries in 2018 (World Bank) falls in the 65%-80% range: Canada 78% and US 82%. After calculation using this data, for the consumption part of GDP, the demand for the manufactured goods as a share of GDP is 30.5% for Canada, and 29.5% for the US. This number in theory needs to be met by domestic production of manufactured goods, plus merchandise imports minus exports. Therefore, if domestic production is too low and there is a low export capacity, the country will most likely have to run trade deficits.

Figure 40. Consumption of Manufactured Goods in all Consumption, UNIDO, 2018

- Can service sectors offset the manufacturing sector to balance the trade?

Service exports though growing faster, comprises a small portion of total exports. Therefore, the service sector cannot offset the loss in the manufacturing to balance the trade in the foreseeable future. Over the past decade, Canadian service exports have been expanding at an annual rate of more than 4%, double the 2% growth rate for exports of goods. In 2018, physical goods, like commodities and manufactured goods, still comprised the vast majority of Canadian exports (Export Development Canada). Canadian goods exports in 2018 went up 6.5% to \$585 billion, with export prices increasing by 2.2% and export volumes expanding by 4.1%. Meanwhile, Canadian service exports grew for the ninth consecutive year, up 5.8%, to reach \$121 billion. For comparison, the amount of Canada’s services exports is about 20% of goods exported. Alarmingly, Canada’s services trade has also run a trade deficit for the past decade. Therefore, it’s not realistic to rely on service exports to fill the gap in the next 10 to 20 years. The low level of goods exported because of the low output from the manufacturing sector, and the limited export capacity of the service sector, makes it hard for Canada to maintain a trade balance. Additionally, a report of IMF (2018) highlights that current barriers to international trade in services are much higher than for goods, and should be reduced so that the expansion of highly-productive service sectors businesses are not constrained by relying solely on domestic demand.

- Can natural resources offset the manufacturing sector to balance the trade?

As per Cross’ calculation (Cross 2015), natural-resource related exports totalled \$308.4 billion, equivalent to 58.3% of all merchandise exports as of 2014. However, this number also includes natural-resource related manufactured products such as refined petroleum energy products or fabricated metal products. Meanwhile, exports of natural resource commodities are subject to dramatic price changes. For example, from 2014 to 2016, the volume of energy product exports dropped by over 50% simply because of the crude oil price collapse (Statistics Canada). Additionally, counting on natural resources may exacerbate the “Dutch

Disease” that says high commodity prices can lead to an appreciation of exchange rate, and consequently crowds out trade-sensitive sectors, particularly manufacturing.

4.4 Global Competitiveness

The World Economic Forum publishes the Global Competitiveness report yearly which “assesses each country’s progress against the full set of factors that determine productivity”, including infrastructure, ICT adoption, macroeconomic stability, labour market, innovation capability, etc. This means that the productivity of a country implies its global competitiveness. As we have described in Section 4.1, historically the Canadian manufacturing sector had a higher growth rate in both labour and multi-factor productivities than the average business sector. The manufacturing sector also has a higher level of productivity. Between 2000 and 2008, the nominal manufacturing output as a share of GDP dropped from 17% to 10%, while the productivity growth of the manufacturing sector also slowed down. As a result, the decline of the manufacturing sector went hand in hand with the slowdown of productivity growth in Canada.

Figure 41. Business Expenditure of R&D, Canada vs others, 1981-2011. (CCA 2013)

At the same time, Canada’s R&D expenditures, which is an important determinant to productivity growth plummeted simultaneously with the decline of the manufacturing sector. As shown in Figure 41, between 2001 and 2011, the share of Canada’s business expenditures on R&D started to drop from its peak, and now lags behind other OECD countries. Why did this happen? The research of the Federal Reserve of St. Louis (Santacreu and Zhu 2018) which studied 24 countries in the OECD for the period of 2000-2014, found that

on average the manufacturing sector contributed to 92.01% of exports, 64.86% of R&D spending, and 42.32% of productivity growth. Au (2004) found that in 2001, the R&D expenditures by the manufacturing sector represented 70% of all industrial R&D expenditures in Canada (Industrial R&D is the private sector’s investment in the development of new ideas, technologies, and processes). Additionally, Au found that the R&D intensity for the manufacturing sector is about four times greater than that of the business sector in Canada (Figure 32). The Council of Canadian Academies (CCA 2013) published a report on “the state of industrial R&D in Canada” which confirmed Au’s findings and claimed that the smaller relative size of the manufacturing sector has accounted for the decline in Canada’s R&D intensity since 2000 (See Figure 42).

Decomposition of Changes in Economy

	Share of the business sector		R&D intensity		Intensity effect	Structural effect
	2000	2008	2000	2008		
	(%)		(%)		Percentage points	
Agriculture, forestry, fishing & hunting	2.88	2.41	0.42	0.48	0.00	0.00
Mining and oil & gas extraction	7.91	13.37	0.30	0.63	0.04	0.03
Utilities	3.41	2.98	0.64	0.63	0.00	0.00
Construction	6.45	9.30	0.10	0.11	0.00	0.00
Manufacturing	24.36	15.01	4.52	4.45	-0.01	-0.42
Services	55.00	56.92	0.81	1.13	0.18	0.02
Business sector	100.00	100.00	1.61	1.44	0.21	-0.38
Sum				-0.17		-0.17

Data source: Panel calculations based on data from Statistics Canada (2012b, 2013d)

Figure 42. Industrial R&D Intensity of Canada by Sector, 1999 vs 2006. (CCA 2013)

Specifically, the OECD classifies manufacturing industries as low-, medium-, or high-technology based on industrial R&D intensities and the propensity to buy equipment for R&D. As shown in Figure 43, we can see a significant drop, especially in the value added share of high- and medium-technology manufacturing industries in Canada between 1999 and 2006, as the manufacturing sector declined. The report by the CCA (2013) mentioned above argues that the decline of the share accounted for by high- and medium-technology manufacturing industries is responsible for the manufacturing sector’s lowered industrial R&D intensity, which has led to lower manufacturing productivity and overall productivity.

All of this implies that the decline of the manufacturing sector, especially the loss in high- and medium-technology manufacturing industries has harmed Canada and will continue to negatively impact our global competitiveness if this trend continues.

		High- technology industries	High- and medium-high technology industries	Low- technology industries
Canada	Value added share (%)			
	2006	1.35	4.64	6.21
	1999	2.03	7.89	7.94
	Average growth	-5.72	-7.30	-3.43
	IR&D intensity (%)			
	2006	29.82	10.94	2.02
	1999	27.15	8.30	0.63
	Average growth	1.35	4.02	18.11

Figure 43. Manufacturing Industries' Share of the Economy and IR&D intensities, Canada. (CCA 2013)

More importantly, as we have mentioned in Section 4.1, many countries are rapidly shifting toward industry 4.0 and advanced manufacturing technologies, such as autonomous robots, integrated computational materials engineering, digital manufacturing, industrial internet and flexible automation, and additive manufacturing (BCG 2015). These emerging technologies will largely increase productivity and thus promote the competitiveness of Canadian exports/products in the international market. Canada also released the “Five Superclusters Strategy” in 2018 to foster advanced manufacturing in order to boost productivity and create a significant number of high-paying jobs. Therefore, to develop advanced manufacturing, Canada needs a healthy and robust manufacturing sector as the base.

4.5 Social Impacts

- Economic inequality

As described in Section 4.2, manufacturing jobs tend to provide decent pay and benefits, especially for workers with lower education. The sudden collapse in the share of manufacturing employment in the 2000s in theory would put these workers in an economic disadvantage, and this may exacerbate the economic inequality. As analyzed in Section 2.2, manufacturing jobs were reduced largely due to import competition and offshoring. Breau and Rigby (2009) claimed that import competition from low-income countries has had a significant impact on wage inequality in Canada, pushing down the wages of less-educated workers relative to those of highly educated workers. Bivens (2013) found that in the US, trade with low-wage countries was responsible for 90% of the growth in the college wage premium since 1995 (the college wage premium is the percent by which wages of college graduates exceed those of workers without a college

degree (roughly 100 million workers)). He also found that the growth of trade with China was responsible for more than half of the growth in the college wage premium in that period. It should be noted that economic inequality does not solely come from trade (or loss of manufacturing jobs), but also from other factors such as skill-biased technological changes, institutional changes such as deregulation. Here we only want to address the impact of the decline in the manufacturing sector.

- **Family and marriage**

As mentioned above, the loss of manufacturing jobs put some workers at an economic disadvantage, which may bring negative impacts to their families. Autor and Dorn (2019) found that the onslaught of imports in the period since 2000 delivered an unprecedented attack on the ability of semi-skilled and unskilled men to find a job and bring home a good paycheck in manufacturing areas. They claim that “shrinking the pool of marriageable low-education men has eroded the incentive for men to maintain committed relationships, curtailed women’s gains from marriage and strengthened men’s bargaining position vis-a-vis casual sex, out-of-wedlock childbirth and non-custodial parenting.” As a consequence, these social changes weaken the appeal of marriage to women and lead to more single-parent families. Research from Klein, Schuh, and Triest (2003) shows that such large-scale shocks have persistent adverse effects on affected communities and their residents, though these costs are rarely fully considered in policy making.

- **Health and mortality**

Health issues might arise in areas competing most directly with imports, especially if workers experience sharper or longer-term declines in employment and real income. Ruhm (2000) reported a positive relationship between the unemployment rate and suicide in a collection of US states, and Sullivan and von Wachter (2009), found that high-tenure workers displaced as part of a mass layoff had a sharp increase in their probability of death. Classen and Dunn (2011) found that unemployment duration is a major force in the relationship between job loss and suicide. In 2015, Case and Deaton (2015) noticed that mortality of white middle-age Americans has been increasing between 1998 and 2013, due to an epidemic of suicides and afflictions stemming from substance abuse. Pierce and Schott (2016) found that US counties more exposed to a exogenous trade liberalization (more import competition and offshoring) exhibit higher rates of suicide and related causes of death, concentrated among whites, especially white males, which used to have disproportionately high employment in manufacturing. These more-exposed counties experienced relative declines in manufacturing employment. They also examined other causes of death that might be related to labor market disruption.

4.6 Other Impacts

- **Domestic political polarization**

It has long been recognized that voters align their political behaviors in line with economic assessments (Key and Donovan 2017). In fact, several political science theories such as “pocketbook hypothesis” or “group hypothesis” describe the economic influence behind the political behaviours. A survey conducted by the Pew Research Center in 2019 found that the US partisan division has deepened. Political extremes such as right-wing populism and left-wing socialism are getting espoused more now, than they were 20 years ago. Even though the reasons for increasing political polarization vary, the increasing economic inequality resulting from the loss of manufacturing jobs, as mentioned in Section 4.5 played a role. Autor et al (2015) found strong evidence that congressional districts exposed to larger increases in import penetration disproportionately removed moderate representatives from office in the 2000s. They found that trade-exposed districts with an initial majority white population or initially in Republican hands became substantially more likely to elect a conservative Republican, while trade-exposed districts with an initial majority-minority population or initially in Democratic hands also become more likely to elect a liberal Democrat. In US presidential elections, districts with greater trade exposure shifted towards the Republican candidate. They interpret these results as supporting a political economy literature that connects adverse economic conditions to support for nativist or extreme politicians. Although there is not a significant amount of similar academic research in Canada, a report from the Digital Democracy Project at McGill University shows that Canada is also becoming more politically polarized in recent years.

- **National security and supply chain security**

As the decline of the manufacturing sector continues, North America will have to rely heavily on foreign imports, nearly half of which come from China - nearly US\$ 58 billion for Canada and US\$600 billion for the US in 2018, including many vital products such as medical supplies, drugs, computers and electronics, machinery, etc. As China is moving towards an increasingly adversarial and less reliable state, as it attempts to challenge the liberal international order, consequently, the risks to the supply chain security cannot be underestimated. During the 2020 global pandemic, many PPE (Personal Protection Equipment) producing countries restricted exports of relevant products. Two Canadian planes that went to pick up PPE equipment from China were reportedly forced to leave empty (CBC 2020). All of this raises supply chain security concerns.

The defence industry may also become vulnerable as it relies on supply chains from many civilian manufacturing sectors. Initially, this may seem to be more of a US issue. However, as the US and Canada

belong to the same defence umbrella (for example, NATO), and Canada heavily participates in the US defence industry, Canada should not neglect it. As the decline of the manufacturing sector continues, those sectors tasked with supplying the military will be weakened and assailable if they have to exist alone. The rapid growth of US imports of computer and electronic parts from China also represents a threat to national security, because it is connected to the outsourcing of US defense products, as explained by Brigadier General John Adams (2015). The outsourcing of the defense industry makes the United States vulnerable to a disruption of supply chains for key missile and communications components. Outsourcing has also reduced the quality of military equipment: a congressional report found nearly 1 million counterfeit components in the supply chain for “critical” defense systems (Senate Armed Services Committee 2012). Outsourcing has eroded the capacity of the defense industry for cost innovation, knowledge generation, and support for domestic employment (Alliance for American Manufacturing 2016).

5. Policy Implications

5.1 A Realistic Vision

So far we have analyzed the causes for the decline of Canada’s manufacturing sector and why it matters (both the decline and the sector itself). Before we propose concrete policy suggestions, we must come up with a realistic vision for the future, which will be illustrated below in a set of outcome-oriented goals.

Goal 1: 15% as a share of GDP in ten years

- As we describe in Section 2, manufacturing powerhouses such as Germany, Japan, South Korea, Taiwan and China all have more than 20% of manufacturing output as a share of GDP. In 2017, Innovation, Science and Economic Development (ISED) Canada set a goal to increase manufacturing sales by 50% by 2030. We prefer using the percentage share of GDP as the measure and to set a more aggressive goal. This is because our research systematically highlights the importance of the manufacturing sector, more than any other literature did. While we admit that 10% for Canada is too low, we also believe 20% is difficult to achieve. Therefore, we believe 15% in ten years is a reasonable target.

Goal 2: 80% increase of merchandise exports in ten years

- As the manufacturing sector declined, a consistent trade deficit followed. We have shown the relationship between the two and the negative impacts of a consistent trade deficit. Therefore, we propose to increase manufacturing exports which will shrink the deficit, assuming the domestic demand for imports remains stable. We have proposed that manufacturing output as a share of GDP will be aimed at 15% from the

current 10%, however, it is hard to do the same for manufacturing exports, as exports are not counted by value-added, but the total value at the border (creates double counting) as described in Section 2. Since Canada's merchandise exports grew by around 50% from 2010 to 2020, we propose an 80% increase in merchandise exports by 2030.

Goal 3: Output of advanced manufacturing doubles in ten years

- The fourth industrial revolution has been championed in lots of industrialized countries. It provides high-pay jobs and contributes significantly to productivity growth. As advanced manufacturing emerges, we expect it to perform better than the overall sector.

Goal 4: Productivity and R&D spending converge with the US in ten years (except for computers and electronics)

- As we describe in Section 2, Canada has a similar economic structure as the US. However, its productivity and R&D spending, which used to be similar, has diverged from the US since the early 2000s. We believe catching up with the US is an appropriate target. While the US has a much larger market and thus the economy of scale, Canadian export firms also get access to the US market as well as the markets of other trading partners. Meanwhile, our goal is based on the assumption that the US keeps its current policy and Canada will adopt a more aggressive one. Additionally, as described in Section 2, the major divergence between Canadian and US productivity is in computers and electronics. Consequently, we can leave this sub-sector out of our goal.

Goal 5: "Made in Canada" output doubles in ten years

- Here, "Made in Canada" means final branded products manufactured in Canada, not supply chains. Many Canadian manufacturers are suppliers for US manufacturing firms, which means a lot of the profit from brand values, innovation, design and marketing are not captured by Canadian firms. The total manufacturing output share will increase from 10% to 15%, considering the underlying GDP will also grow, by a 2% annualized rate until 2030, the manufacturing output will increase by over 80%. Therefore, we propose the output of "Made in Canada" doubles by the year 2030.

5.2 Policy Suggestions

In the first part of Section 5, we proposed a realistic vision of the goals for Canada's manufacturing sector within the next ten years. We have clearly seen the decline of this sector since the early 2000s, as well as

the important role it plays in the economy and society. It's important to recognize the challenges the manufacturing sector faces. According to a report by the Canadian Manufacturers & Exporters (CME, 2020), which is Canada's largest trade and industry association, slow output growth, low investments, chronic trade deficit from weak export growth and a decline in global competitiveness are the major concerns for the sector. Calls for government support, though not all the same, are much aligned with our suggestions below, including the procurement plan, support for business investments, "Made in Canada" campaign, tax incentives, reducing the cost of doing business, improving regional value-chains, and leveraging Canada's natural assets, etc. Our policy suggestions try to address their concerns as much as possible, as well as provide solutions/response to our research findings. In addition to academic research, we also look at examples such as Germany, the US and China, to see if there are some useful policies or lessons that can apply to Canada. For example, the Industrie 4.0 of Germany and the US Advanced Manufacturing Initiative are reviewed. In this part, we will discuss actions that can be taken to reach these goals. The main initiatives are structured around the following four points:

1. Trade - pursue new or fair trade deals for Canadian manufacturers, to allow them access to bigger markets and compete on a level playing field both domestically and internationally, and thus boost the demand for their products.
2. Financial support - provide financial incentives to the manufacturing sector to encourage investments, research and entrepreneurship, especially in advanced manufacturing.
3. Government assistance - provide mentoring assistance for the development of the manufacturing sector.
4. Labour market - address the labour market concerns for the manufacturing sector.

Action 1. Rethinking trade policy by moving towards fair trade.

As per our analysis in Section 3, the collapse of the manufacturing sector after the 2000s in both Canada and the US was largely due to the import competition and offshoring, especially from China. China's unfair trade practices significantly exacerbated the decline, which resulted in a huge trade deficit. Unfair trade deals and practices inevitably put Canadian manufacturing firms at a (sometimes fatal) disadvantage whether in domestic or global markets. Most trade theories build upon real free trade amongst trading partners as mentioned in Section 3. One trade partner breaking the rules will be at the cost of others. As claimed by the office of US Trade Representative (2019), some of the current WTO rules applied to the economic conditions back in the early 1990's, but do not apply today and need to be reformed. As China has become the world's factory with a labour force of nearly 900 million and is also quickly climbing up the value chain, these unfair trade advantages can in theory lead to more Canadian manufacturing firms

being pushed out of business. By correcting unfair trade practices, jobs and firms which couldn't otherwise compete can reshore. Otherwise, Canada's remaining comparative advantages such as in transportation or pharmaceuticals may have the same fate as others, which have gone or been off-shored since the early 2000s. It is therefore required that the Canadian government do the following:

Action 1.1 Hold bilateral or multilateral trade talks (together with countries with similar objectives) with China and any other non-complying countries to discuss its trade practices and enforcement, though we recognize that it is hard for China to comply. The Government of Canada has not taken similar actions as of today. Canada has been tough during the negotiations of USMCA or CPTPP, and retaliates immediately to US's tariffs, so it seems counterproductive if the negative trade behaviour of China is not corrected. Canada wanted to make a free trade deal with China before the Meng Wanzhou incident (the Government of Canada website). Currently, the trade relationship with China has been mostly running under the WTO framework. Fairness (maybe reciprocity) should be the goal of trade deals. Canada's trading partners should ideally be countries that have the rule of law, which means they will honour deals and protect basic human rights. For developed countries, they should also have similar standards as Canada for labour rights and environmental protection. This is what the CPTPP was designed to do, which is a trade bloc with a higher standard for both developed and developing countries.

Action 1.2 Work with the WTO to push reforms which should include effective monitoring and enforcement mechanisms. As stated above, some of the WTO's rules are regarded as outdated. Very often certain members have hidden violations, such as export subsidies and non-tariff barriers as described in Section 3. It is difficult for other members to be aware of these hidden behaviours. The dispute-settlement mechanism of the WTO can last up to 15 months and there are no provisions to expel a member if it's a constant bad player (according to the WTO website). Currently, Canada together with 12 countries have formed the Ottawa Group (Global Affairs Canada) to push for WTO reforms, however, these requests mostly fall into dispute-settlement mechanisms. Further to this, we argue that the WTO reforms should include a way to effectively punish countries who have constantly used unfair trade practices and even human rights violations, with consequences that include membership divestment. It would also make less sense to stay in the CPTPP which has higher standards, while some lower standard WTO members can easily access the majority of Canada's market. Higher standards put Canada at a disadvantage in terms of global competition by increasing costs.

Action 1.3 As Canada and the US have substantive comparative advantages in some service sectors, such as information, healthcare, education and finance. Canada should work with trading partners or the WTO to ratify the rules of trade, to largely enhance service trade, especially with the digital economy getting

bigger. According to the provisions listed on their website, the CPTPP and CETA set a good example for service trade rules, but can do more with a wider range of trading partners.

Action 1.4 The federal government should actively pursue new trade deals with overseas markets. The government should also expand the promotion of Canadian exports (such as trade shows), and encourage Canadian firms to label products with maple leaves as a symbol of quality, as proposed by the CME. Current programs such as “CanExport” provide support for export marketing and international expansion activities. “CanExport” helps exporters improve their sales and brand exposure in international markets through trade shows, marketing activities, packaging modifications, and market research. They also offer up to a 75% rebate for eligible expenses or \$75,000 in cost matching funds per application. Based on our goals, we are proposing to increase the limit to \$100,000. Also note that although trade diversification is important, this does not mean blindly allowing in bad players. Canada has a medium sized economy, so it does not need the entire world for its economy to thrive. Additionally, the withdrawal of the US should allow Canada to play a leading role in the CPTPP and actively engage members who are willing to obey the rules. Potential partner countries include Taiwan, Thailand, South Korea and the United Kingdom, all of which have reportedly expressed interest (Wikipedia - CPTPP).

Action 1.5 Take measures such as direct funding or tax credits to encourage Canadian firms to reshore manufacturing plants as much as possible, as shown in Section 4 the importance not only in economics, but also in social and security, among other aspects. The fact that these firms exist in Canada implies they have competitive advantages in their areas. They offshored manufacturing because it saved them money on labour costs, as described in Section 3. Bringing back these manufacturing is easier and more realistic than building in a totally new area. It is reported that the Japanese and the US governments are providing direct funding to help their overseas companies reshore in the wake of COVID-19. So far, the Government of Canada has not taken similar actions.

Action 2. The federal or provincial/territorial government provides financial incentives to attract business investments.

High costs are impediments to manufacturing firms for investment and expansion. A report of the manufacturing cost index provided by the Boston Consulting Group in 2014 describes the direct costs in the manufacturing sector. The non-labour costs (natural gas, electricity and others) are significantly lower for both Canada and the US than Germany, Japan, Korea, Taiwan and China. Labour cost is still the factor that creates the biggest disparity in total manufacturing costs among countries, though getting narrower. Production that uses more industrial robots or other automation technology which make overall

manufacturing cost lower, can bring more firms back or establish new firms. Although it could eliminate more routine-based workers, it will also create more high-tech jobs, as well as increase manufacturing productivity and output.

Harju et al. (2012) published a NBER paper that found that a lower marginal tax rate for entrepreneurs in Finland statistically increased their gross revenue. Some literature has stated that more progressive income taxation reduces the firms' willingness to take risk, thus leading to less entrepreneurial activity (Kerr and Nanda 2009) and lower economic growth (Cullen and Gordon 2007). Benmarker et al. (2009) found that wages increased as a result of the abolition of payroll tax, but employment did not. Duranton et al. (2011) find that increases in tax rates can reduce the labor demand of firms.

An OECD report (2017) on tax credit benefits for R&D spending notes that tax incentives tied to performance such as in employment gains or investment can encourage increased spending for all types of companies, sectors and research. Tax credits can encourage R&D investments for both large and small firms, and refundable tax credits are especially effective for small firms without taxable income.

Given the current low level of manufacturing output as a share of GDP and the other factors such as a low level of business R&D investment and the high cost of labour, it will be difficult for manufacturing firms to have a meaningful breakthrough without financial incentives. The manufacturing sector is important to productivity growth and global competitiveness, so it is worthy of special treatment. Many other countries have used incentives such as tax credits to encourage investment in specific industries. For example, China has been using this approach for a long time. According to the Chinese Central Government (official website), the profit tax rate for manufacturers has been 16%, lower than the all sector average of 25%. In 2019, it was further cut to 13%. Advanced manufacturers enjoy a 15% tax rate and recently, China issued a policy that will give all semiconductor manufacturing firms a zero tax rate for five years. We propose several concrete actions in this section:

Action 2.1 Each level of government should consider a certain amount of meaningful tax rate cuts or tax credits for all manufacturing firms, especially for advanced manufacturing firms. Also, a refundable tax credit for startups for the first two years, since they may not have taxable income. It will be paid back from future tax revenue when Canada has a thriving manufacturing sector and the spillover benefits in other sectors. As a result of more manufacturers choosing to stay, R&D business such as product design on top of manufacturing will also likely stay. If Canada does not actively provide incentives, the manufacturing sector which has proven to be important, will not thrive again by itself. By looking at other jurisdictions, the Industrie 4.0 in Germany proposes tax incentives for its advanced industry. Germany also suggests a regular monitoring of taxation in other countries to determine its attractiveness for business. In fact, some

provinces already provide tax incentives. For example, Ontario and Quebec have tax credits for manufacturing and processing sectors in equipment purchase (Ontario & Quebec government websites). In 2018, the Government of Canada set up the “Accelerated Investment Incentive”, which allows businesses to claim up to three times the amount of a deduction for machinery and equipment used in the manufacturing, which is applicable in the first year (Government of Canada). However, judging from the current situation (stagnation of this sector), we suggest the government enhances the program or at least reexamines the effects of these incentives, as well as assess what global counterparts are doing. In terms of the corporate income tax rate, currently the federal rate stands at 15%, provincial and territorial ones vary. Only three provinces or territories, Ontario, Saskatchewan and Yukon have lower tax rates for manufacturing and processing firms than others. For example, in 2020 Ontario’s corporate income tax rate is 1.5% lower for manufacturing firms (10% vs. 11.5%). We suggest all levels of governments consider further lowering corporate income tax rates for manufacturing firms. The level could be determined through annually examining the sector’s performance by surveys and against the metric goals.

Action 2.2 Each level of government recapitalizes initiative funds to encourage and foster startups and entrepreneurs in the manufacturing sector. The fund can be used to help invest in equipment purchases and early stage R&D. Governments can share a royalty based on sales after commercialization. In 2020, Germany is reportedly establishing a 2 billion euro fund for its startups (Reuters 2020). Currently the government of Canada has similar programs such “ISC” (Innovative Solutions Canada) which provides government grants and procurement contracts to stimulate technology research, development, and commercialization of startups and SMEs. These initiative funds are aligning with our policies, and we suggest governments keep monitoring the performance of the sector and its counterparts (such as Germany) to continuously adjust policies as needed, especially for the manufacturing sector. Additionally, the application process should be streamlined and decisions on funding approval should be made within a short timeframe. Private capital can also be mobilized by investing in manufacturing startups. Several Canadian cities in Canada such as Toronto, Ottawa, Vancouver and Montreal are abundant in venture capital (the NGen report mentioned below, 2019). Governments can work with these investors to encourage their investment in startups in the manufacturing sector.

Action 2.3 Governments provide tax credits and grants to reward the R&D activities of manufacturing firms, for example, eligible activities include those who adopt newer technologies (e.g., deploying an expected amount of industry robots per capita), among other R&D activities. The German government is set to provide tax breaks for research (Industrie 4.0). However, we do not recommend artificially picking winner areas, especially subsidies to specific companies. Government funds should be open to the entire manufacturing sector or advanced manufacturing as a whole, or to whomever wants to become an entrant.

In 2017, the Government of Canada established the “Innovation Superclusters Initiative” investing up to \$950 million to support business-led innovation superclusters, which includes advanced manufacturing clusters. The NGen (Next Generation) Advanced Manufacturing program from this initiative supports collaborative technology development and project applications, which offsets up to 45% of eligible project expenses. It engages with industry through memberships, so that the eligible firms can reimburse their R&D costs and are inclined to increase investments. In NGen’s official report, from 2018 to 2023, it is expected to receive \$53 million from supporting organizations and other government agencies. Also note, NGen is focused on advanced manufacturing, not the entire manufacturing sector. Other programs such as SIF (Strategic Innovation Fund) are more about innovation and determine eligibility from potential growth, therefore, they are not specifically targeted at manufacturing firms. Manufacturing firms may not perform like high-tech startups, which can grow dramatically in a short time frame. The CME also calls for the expansion of the SIF. Again, we suggest governments recapitalize the funding amount for programs such as NGen or SIF, especially for the entire manufacturing sector (not only advanced manufacturing). Also, the government should keep monitoring performance and continuously adjust the levels of funding and scope of eligible firms.

Action 2.4 Direct a certain part of government procurement to “Made in Canada”, in order to boost the demand for Canadian manufactured goods, especially in healthcare since it's the largest spending budget item in every provincial government (For example, the Government of Ontario). This will foster a strong healthcare related manufacturing sector, which is what the CME calls for. This is not a restrictive “Buy Canada” approach, as that can create negative frictions in an open and relatively small economy like Canada. This policy is to incorporate domestic content provisions to reward bidders for leveraging domestic content by improving their bid scores. Such approaches are successfully used in Europe (see the EU’s procurement Directives) and in California.

Action 3. Governments provide mentoring assistance for the manufacturing sector

Besides financial incentives, governments should play a leading role in the strategic renaissance of the manufacturing sector. Governmental assistance ranges from infrastructure and industrial park zoning, to a high-level development strategy and industrial policies. In such a competitive global environment where lots of governments behave aggressively to support industry, strategies and plans for Canadian manufacturing firms cannot compete without government’s assistance, at least not in the recovery phase. The mentoring assistance we propose includes:

Action 3.1 Governments work with the industry to develop a growth strategy that identifies national/regional comparative advantages, which can be based on existing performance, market and technology analysis, as well as the estimated future potential. For example, aerospace and automotive manufacturing are two areas where Canada is competitive. We acknowledge that an advanced manufacturing supercluster strategy (run by the NGen), which has a five-year strategy to accelerate development, adoption, and the scaling-up of world-leading capabilities in advanced manufacturing. This program/strategy consists of leadership to identify the challenges, opportunities, trends, and priorities; connections among manufacturers and technology providers; collaboration and partnership opportunities for Canadian companies; funding; and facilitated access to the services, tools, testbeds, and training programs. We agree with these functionalities that NGen provides. However, as mentioned, NGen is more about advanced manufacturing. As stated in Section 4.4, advanced manufacturing needs a healthy manufacturing sector as its base. Therefore, we need a holistic strategy for the entire manufacturing sector as well.

Action 3.2 Governments work with industry and academia to develop an advanced manufacturing plan, which includes establishing institutions that undertake research on advanced manufacturing technologies, helping manufacturing firms adapt technologies to their production lines, and incorporating all Canadian manufacturers to accelerate the diffusion of the latest technologies (technology awareness). Diffusion of automation technology is especially important, since one of the biggest disadvantages of Canada's manufacturing sector is labour cost, and one of the biggest advantages is access to raw materials and energy supply. With the widespread adoption of automation and industry robots, many firms, even those who make low-value added products such as plastics and clothing can thrive with the benefit of scale and saved labour cost. An automation diffusion center can be established. Examples of an advanced manufacturing plan are the US Advanced Manufacturing Initiative, Germany's Industrie 4.0, and China's Made in China 2025 and the China Standards 2035. Examples of research institutions include Germany's Fraunhofer Society and Manufacturing USA, which is a network of 14 research institutes. They not only mentor and collaborate with firms, but also conduct cutting-edge advanced manufacturing research. As stated on the official website, NGen is a non-profit organization that is responsible for running the Advanced Manufacturing Supercluster program and matches manufacturing companies with new technologies. As many SMEs do not have the ability to develop their own advanced manufacturing technologies, such as advanced materials, industrial internet and additive manufacturing, it is desirable that NGen be extended to advanced manufacturing research and diffuse technologies to member firms. Also note that these publicly funded research institutes, as well as other publicly funded universities or projects should not be used by foreign companies as their "R&D department", or under the title of "cooperation". Negative examples of this

include Huawei's research with 13 Canadian publicly funded universities. Institutes funded by Canadian tax dollars should serve Canadian firms and help them capitalize. Under international agreements led by governments, these research institutes can cooperate with leading countries such as Germany, Japan and the US on technology standards, information exchange, among other co-operations. In March 2020, China and Germany co-issued a white paper on "Functional Safety for Industrie 4.0 and Intelligent Manufacturing".

Action 3.3 Governments work with industry to divide regions into industry areas, such as automotives, pharmaceuticals, aerospace, etc and facilitate zone planning for industry parks, so that firms can cooperate more effectively with each other and realize the benefits of an economy of scale. As per the CME report, investors often feel limited in terms of location options. More planned industrial parks can also boost the local economies and help realize their economic potential. Additionally, governments should ensure facilities include electricity, gas, transportation, internet, amongst others. Abundant natural resources are the upstream supply for the manufacturing sector, which is the competitive advantage Canada has. Governments should try to ensure that energy prices are attractive to firms by reducing red tape in the energy sector, as well as to secure the supply of raw materials, making Canada stand out compared to global competitors. NGen's strategy deals with infrastructure, but it is more about the technology/IT infrastructure for advanced manufacturing, not for the entire manufacturing sector.

Action 3.4 Governments continuously work with industry experts to identify and cut unnecessary red tape for the manufacturing sector, and take efforts to improve the ease of doing businesses. According to the Ease of Doing Business Rank of the World Bank, Canada has been on a declining trend in this rank for the past decade. Examples of red tape include those on the labour market, administrative processes, environment, etc. Currently, several provincial governments such as Ontario and Alberta have started to cut red tape (the Government of Ontario and Government of Alberta websites). But these initiatives are directed to all sectors and do not have a specific focus. We suggest both federal and provincial/territorial governments conduct a specific examination of red tape in the manufacturing sector, because of its importance to the overall economy. Additionally, governments should continuously examine relevant laws, such as competition laws to encourage business competition in the manufacturing sector.

Action 3.5 The CME proposes in its report that governments introduce an export tax incentive that lowers corporate tax rates on export sales to encourage exports. We don't agree with this policy, because it may violate the WTO's export subsidies prohibition (the WTO website), and will cause deadweight losses. Rather, we agree with the CME that governments should significantly expand export mentorship peer councils by at least fourfold to improve the free exchange of information and know-how within the private sector and increase support for B2B linkages to support SME expansion from local suppliers into global

value chains. Firms should easily be aware of or be proactively approached by these agencies to be informed on the dynamics of the international market. For example, when TD Bank wanted to set up a joint venture in India, they were getting nowhere with the Indian Government. So TD Bank approached Global Affairs and was introduced to the right people in India. These government agencies can help companies navigate the tricky rules of dealing with other countries. Additionally, governments should work to lower interprovincial trade barriers with the goal of having a single domestic market. To the best of our knowledge, Canada currently does not have such agencies, and interprovincial trade barriers still exist (Senate Canada, 2019)

Action 4. Governments work with the industry and educational institutions to develop educational and training programs.

Based on surveys by the CME, 40% of manufacturing firms face labour and skills shortages. The governments should do more to address the concerns of firms about labour market gaps. There are not enough students who are pursuing post-secondary programs that will prepare them for jobs in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics, these skills are required to pursue careers in advanced manufacturing (NGen 2019). What's more concerning, Canadian talent is sometimes being hired by foreign companies for R&D, since they cannot find enough job postings from local firms. As mentioned above, Huawei has several R&D centers in Canada, has hired hundreds of people, and has research relationships with 13 Canadian universities as their "R&D departments". Approaches the government should undertake to address labour market concerns include:

Action 4.1 Governments work with industry and post-secondary institutions to provide training to displaced, existing and future workers. Training can include government sponsored courses, programs and apprenticeships. There are several programs such as the "Canada Job Grant" and "Hiring Grants" which are government funded and designed to reduce the costs of providing third-party skills training to new and existing employees or provide meaningful work experience in a particular field. However, the manufacturing labour market has special characteristics, so we suggest governments consider a dedicated job training program for the manufacturing sector. For example, lots of manufacturing jobs do not need higher education, so working with colleges and even high schools can be emphasized. Attracting and training people who have lower education or who have dropped out of the labour force is also an option. The NGen has a training plan, but again it mostly focuses on STEM education and advanced manufacturing.

Action 4.2 Governments work with industry to identify labour needs and add them to the current immigration system, specifically in the “Skilled Worker” stream. To the best of our knowledge, the Government of Canada does not have a specific immigration policy for this purpose.

Action 4.3 Governments launch or expand OpenDoors programs for grades 7 - 9 students to showcase local manufacturing and products, to increase the awareness of the importance of manufacturing and reduce existing prejudices against the sector. Manufacturing has been regarded by many as a sunset sector in developed countries and this thinking has not improved much today. These programs not only create awareness about what goods are made in Canada, but they also promote careers in the industry, which is essential for attracting the next generation of workers, as well as fostering a mentality or culture in society.

6. Conclusion

In this research paper, we have shown the descriptive statistics of Canada’s manufacturing sector from which we can clearly see a declining trend in terms of output, output as a share of GDP and employment. We also investigate the reasons behind the decline. From the early 2000s, import competition and offshoring, especially since China joined the WTO have become the number one cause for the decline. We also explain why this decline matters, from aspects such as the health of the economy, labour market, international trade, global competitiveness, social impacts and others (i.e. political and national security implications). Manufacturing has been driving productivity growth and providing decent-pay jobs for decades and will continue doing so, especially with the advent of advanced manufacturing. Global commodity prices have been low for six straight years since 2015, and Canada cannot rely on this volatile sector, while continuing to lose an important sector like manufacturing. We draw the conclusion that not only does the decline matter, but it’s urgent for the governments to take measures to reverse the trend. Lastly, we provide a realistic vision for Canada's manufacturing sectors and provide a set of policy suggestions. These policy suggestions require a multifaceted approach to turn around the decline in manufacturing and revitalize the sector.

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Appendix

1. Proof

Labour productivity growth equals real output divided by hours worked.

$$P = Y/L$$

Where P is labour productivity, Y is the real output, and L is the hours worked of this year. Let P', Y' and L' be the variables of next year, the labour productivity growth rate is expressed as:

$$(P' - P)/P = (Y'/L' - Y/L)/(Y/L) \quad (1)$$

The difference of real output growth rate and hours worked growth rate is:

$$(Y' - Y)/Y - (L' - L)/L = (Y'L - YL - YL' + YL)/(YL) = (Y'L - YL')/(YL) \quad (2)$$

Divide the numerator and denominator of this by LL', (2) equals:

$$(Y'/L' - Y/L)/(Y/L) = \{[(Y'/L') - (Y/L)]/(Y/L)\} * \{L/L'\} = \{(P' - P)/P\} * \{L/L'\} \quad (3)$$

Combine (2) and (3), we get:

$$(P' - P)/P = \{L/L'\} * [(Y' - Y)/Y - (L' - L)/L]$$

Let L'/L be approximation error, we get:

$$\Delta L/L \approx \Delta Y/Y - \Delta P/P$$